

Manhattan plots for the associations between InDels and VBTs of pregnant women

(adjusted covariates including first-time pregnancy status, baseline gestational age, InDels based PC1 - PC10)

Contents

1	Binary VBTs (The P/A or D/ND of bacterial taxa)	20
1.1	Phenotype 1.	
	p_Actinobacteriota (P/A)	21
1.2	Phenotype 2.	
	p_Firmicutes (D/ND)	22
1.3	Phenotype 3.	
	p_Proteobacteria (P/A)	23
1.4	Phenotype 4.	
	c_Actinobacteria (P/A)	24
1.5	Phenotype 5.	
	c_Clostridia (P/A)	25
1.6	Phenotype 6.	
	c_Gammaproteobacteria (P/A)	26
1.7	Phenotype 7.	
	o_Bacteroidales (P/A)	27
1.8	Phenotype 8.	
	o_Campylobacteriales (P/A)	28
1.9	Phenotype 9.	
	o_Fusobacteriales (P/A)	29
1.10	Phenotype 10.	
	o_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (P/A)	30
1.11	Phenotype 11.	
	f_Aerococcaceae (P/A)	31
1.12	Phenotype 12.	
	f_Bifidobacteriaceae (P/A)	32
1.13	Phenotype 13.	
	f_Lachnospiraceae (P/A)	33

1.14	Phenotype 14.	
	f_Mycoplasmataceae (P/A)	34
1.15	Phenotype 15.	
	f_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (P/A)	35
1.16	Phenotype 16.	
	f_Veillonellaceae (P/A)	36
1.17	Phenotype 17.	
	g_Anaerococcus (P/A)	37
1.18	Phenotype 18.	
	g_Atopobium (P/A)	38
1.19	Phenotype 19.	
	g_Dialister (P/A)	39
1.20	Phenotype 20.	
	g_Lactobacillus (D/ND)	40
1.21	Phenotype 21.	
	g_Megasphaera (P/A)	41
1.22	Phenotype 22.	
	g_Peptoniphilus (P/A)	42
1.23	Phenotype 23.	
	g_Prevotella (P/A)	43
1.24	Phenotype 24.	
	g_Streptococcus (P/A)	44
1.25	Phenotype 25.	
	s_Aerococcus christensenii (P/A)	45
1.26	Phenotype 26.	
	s_Atopobium vaginae (P/A)	46
1.27	Phenotype 27.	
	s_Dialister micraerophilus (P/A)	47
1.28	Phenotype 28.	
	s_Dialister propionicifaciens (P/A)	48
1.29	Phenotype 29.	
	s_Finegoldia magna (P/A)	49
1.30	Phenotype 30.	
	s_Gardnerella vaginalis (P/A)	50
1.31	Phenotype 31.	
	s_Lactobacillus crispatus (D/ND)	51
1.32	Phenotype 32.	
	s_Lactobacillus iners (D/ND)	52
1.33	Phenotype 33.	
	s_Lactobacillus jensenii (P/A)	53
1.34	Phenotype 34.	
	s_Lactobacillus mulieris (P/A)	54
1.35	Phenotype 35.	
	s_Lactobacillus paragasseri/gasseri (P/A)	55

1.36	Phenotype 36.	
	s_Lactobacillus reuteri (P/A)	56
1.37	Phenotype 37.	
	s_Megasphaera genomosp type 1 (P/A)	57
1.38	Phenotype 38.	
	s_Peptoniphilus vaginalis (P/A)	58
1.39	Phenotype 39.	
	s_Prevotella bivia (P/A)	59
1.40	Phenotype 40.	
	s_Prevotella timonensis (P/A)	60
2	Continuous VBTs (Alpha diversity)	60
2.1	Phenotype 1.	
	ASV Richness	61
2.2	Phenotype 2.	
	Shannon Index	62
2.3	Phenotype 3.	
	Faith PD	63
2.4	Phenotype 4.	
	Pielou Evenness	64
3	Continuous VBTs (The extrapolated PICRUSt2 MetaCyc pathways)	64
3.1	Phenotype 1.	
	1CMET2-PWY (N10-formyl-tetrahydrofolate biosynthesis)	65
3.2	Phenotype 2.	
	ALL-CHORISMATE-PWY (superpathway of chorismate metabolism)	66
3.3	Phenotype 3.	
	ANAEROFrucAT-PWY (homolactic fermentation)	67
3.4	Phenotype 4.	
	ANAGLYCOLYSIS-PWY (glycolysis III (from glucose))	68
3.5	Phenotype 5.	
	ARG+POLYAMINE-SYN (superpathway of arginine and polyamine biosynthesis)	69
3.6	Phenotype 6.	
	ARGORNPROST-PWY (arginine, ornithine and proline interconversion)	70
3.7	Phenotype 7.	
	ARGSYN-PWY (L-arginine biosynthesis I (via L-ornithine))	71
3.8	Phenotype 8.	
	ARGSYNBSUB-PWY (L-arginine biosynthesis II (acetyl cycle))	72
3.9	Phenotype 9.	
	ARO-PWY (chorismate biosynthesis I)	73
3.10	Phenotype 10.	
	ASPASN-PWY (superpathway of L-aspartate and L-asparagine biosynthesis)	74
3.11	Phenotype 11.	
	BIOTIN-BIOSYNTHESIS-PWY (biotin biosynthesis I)	75

3.12	Phenotype 12. BRANCHED-CHAIN-AA-SYN-PWY (superpathway of branched amino acid biosynthesis)	76
3.13	Phenotype 13. CALVIN-PWY (Calvin-Benson-Bassham cycle)	77
3.14	Phenotype 14. CATECHOL-ORTHO-CLEAVAGE-PWY (catechol degradation to β-keto adipate)	78
3.15	Phenotype 15. CENTFERM-PWY (pyruvate fermentation to butanoate)	79
3.16	Phenotype 16. COA-PWY (coenzyme A biosynthesis I)	80
3.17	Phenotype 17. COBALSYN-PWY (adenosylcobalamin salvage from cobinamide I)	81
3.18	Phenotype 18. CODH-PWY (reductive acetyl coenzyme A pathway)	82
3.19	Phenotype 19. COLANSYN-PWY (colanic acid building blocks biosynthesis)	83
3.20	Phenotype 20. COMPLETE-ARO-PWY (superpathway of aromatic amino acid biosynthesis)	84
3.21	Phenotype 21. DAPLYSINESYN-PWY (L-lysine biosynthesis I)	85
3.22	Phenotype 22. DENOVOPURINE2-PWY (superpathway of purine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)	86
3.23	Phenotype 23. DTDPRHAMSYN-PWY (dTDP-L-rhamnose biosynthesis I)	87
3.24	Phenotype 24. ENTBACSYN-PWY (enterobactin biosynthesis)	88
3.25	Phenotype 25. FAO-PWY (fatty acid β-oxidation I)	89
3.26	Phenotype 26. FASYN-ELONG-PWY (fatty acid elongation – saturated)	90
3.27	Phenotype 27. FASYN-INITIAL-PWY (superpathway of fatty acid biosynthesis initiation (E. coli))	91
3.28	Phenotype 28. FERMENTATION-PWY (mixed acid fermentation)	92
3.29	Phenotype 29. FOLSYN-PWY (superpathway of tetrahydrofolate biosynthesis and salvage)	93
3.30	Phenotype 30. FUC-RHAMCAT-PWY (superpathway of fucose and rhamnose degradation)	94
3.31	Phenotype 31. FUCCAT-PWY (fucose degradation)	95
3.32	Phenotype 32. GALACT-GLUCUROCAT-PWY (superpathway of hexuronide and hexuronate degradation)	96

3.33	Phenotype 33.	
	GALACTUROCAT-PWY (D-galacturonate degradation I)	97
3.34	Phenotype 34.	
	GLCMANNANAUT-PWY (superpathway of N-acetylglucosamine, N-acetylmannosamine and N-acetylneuraminic acid degradation)	98
3.35	Phenotype 35.	
	GLUCONEO-PWY (gluconeogenesis I)	99
3.36	Phenotype 36.	
	GLUCOSE1PMETAB-PWY (glucose and glucose-1-phosphate degradation)	100
3.37	Phenotype 37.	
	GLUCUROCAT-PWY (superpathway of β -D-glucuronide and D-glucuronate degra- dation)	101
3.38	Phenotype 38.	
	GLUTORN-PWY (L-ornithine biosynthesis)	102
3.39	Phenotype 39.	
	GLYCOCAT-PWY (glycogen degradation I (bacterial))	103
3.40	Phenotype 40.	
	GLYCOGENSYNTH-PWY (glycogen biosynthesis I (from ADP-D-Glucose))	104
3.41	Phenotype 41.	
	GLYCOLYSIS (glycolysis I (from glucose 6-phosphate))	105
3.42	Phenotype 42.	
	GLYCOLYSIS-E-D (superpathway of glycolysis and Entner-Doudoroff)	106
3.43	Phenotype 43.	
	GLYCOLYSIS-TCA-GLYOX-BYPASS (superpathway of glycolysis, pyruvate dehy- drogenase, TCA, and glyoxylate bypass)	107
3.44	Phenotype 44.	
	GLYOXYLATE-BYPASS (glyoxylate cycle)	108
3.45	Phenotype 45.	
	GOLPDLCAT-PWY (superpathway of glycerol degradation to 1,3-propanediol)	109
3.46	Phenotype 46.	
	HEME-BIOSYNTHESIS-II (heme biosynthesis I (aerobic))	110
3.47	Phenotype 47.	
	HEMESYN2-PWY (heme biosynthesis II (anaerobic))	111
3.48	Phenotype 48.	
	HEXITOLDEGSUPER-PWY (superpathway of hexitol degradation (bacteria))	112
3.49	Phenotype 49.	
	HISDEG-PWY (L-histidine degradation I)	113
3.50	Phenotype 50.	
	HISTSYN-PWY (L-histidine biosynthesis)	114
3.51	Phenotype 51.	
	HOMOSER-METSYN-PWY (L-methionine biosynthesis I)	115
3.52	Phenotype 52.	
	HSERMETANA-PWY (L-methionine biosynthesis III)	116

3.53	Phenotype 53.	
	ILEUSYN-PWY (L-isoleucine biosynthesis I (from threonine))	117
3.54	Phenotype 54.	
	KDO-NAGLIPASYN-PWY (superpathway of (Kdo)2-lipid A biosynthesis)	118
3.55	Phenotype 55.	
	LACTOSECAT-PWY (lactose and galactose degradation I)	119
3.56	Phenotype 56.	
	LEU-DEG2-PWY (L-leucine degradation I)	120
3.57	Phenotype 57.	
	MET-SAM-PWY (superpathway of S-adenosyl-L-methionine biosynthesis)	121
3.58	Phenotype 58.	
	METH-ACETATE-PWY (methanogenesis from acetate)	122
3.59	Phenotype 59.	
	NAD-BIOSYNTHESIS-II (NAD salvage pathway II)	123
3.60	Phenotype 60.	
	NAGLIPASYN-PWY (lipid IVA biosynthesis)	124
3.61	Phenotype 61.	
	NONMEVIPP-PWY (methylerythritol phosphate pathway I)	125
3.62	Phenotype 62.	
	NONOXIPENT-PWY (pentose phosphate pathway (non-oxidative branch))	126
3.63	Phenotype 63.	
	OANTIGEN-PWY (O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis (E. coli))	127
3.64	Phenotype 64.	
	P105-PWY (TCA cycle IV (2-oxoglutarate decarboxylase))	128
3.65	Phenotype 65.	
	P108-PWY (pyruvate fermentation to propanoate I)	129
3.66	Phenotype 66.	
	P122-PWY (heterolactic fermentation)	130
3.67	Phenotype 67.	
	P124-PWY (Bifidobacterium shunt)	131
3.68	Phenotype 68.	
	P125-PWY (superpathway of (R,R)-butanediol biosynthesis)	132
3.69	Phenotype 69.	
	P161-PWY (acetylene degradation)	133
3.70	Phenotype 70.	
	P162-PWY (L-glutamate degradation V (via hydroxyglutarate))	134
3.71	Phenotype 71.	
	P163-PWY (L-lysine fermentation to acetate and butanoate)	135
3.72	Phenotype 72.	
	P164-PWY (purine nucleobases degradation I (anaerobic))	136
3.73	Phenotype 73.	
	P221-PWY (octane oxidation)	137
3.74	Phenotype 74.	
	P23-PWY (reductive TCA cycle I)	138

3.75	Phenotype 75.	
	P381-PWY (adenosylcobalamin biosynthesis II (late cobalt incorporation))	139
3.76	Phenotype 76.	
	P4-PWY (superpathway of L-lysine, L-threonine and L-methionine biosynthesis I)	140
3.77	Phenotype 77.	
	P42-PWY (incomplete reductive TCA cycle)	141
3.78	Phenotype 78.	
	P441-PWY (superpathway of N-acetylneuraminate degradation)	142
3.79	Phenotype 79.	
	P461-PWY (hexitol fermentation to lactate, formate, ethanol and acetate)	143
3.80	Phenotype 80.	
	P562-PWY (myo-inositol degradation I)	144
3.81	Phenotype 81.	
	PANTO-PWY (phosphopantothenate biosynthesis I)	145
3.82	Phenotype 82.	
	PANTOSYN-PWY (pantothenate and coenzyme A biosynthesis I)	146
3.83	Phenotype 83.	
	PENTOSE-P-PWY (pentose phosphate pathway)	147
3.84	Phenotype 84.	
	PEPTIDOLYCAN SYN-PWY (peptidoglycan biosynthesis I (meso-diaminopimelate containing))	148
3.85	Phenotype 85.	
	PHOSLIP SYN-PWY (superpathway of phospholipid biosynthesis I (bacteria))	149
3.86	Phenotype 86.	
	POLYAMIN SYN3-PWY (superpathway of polyamine biosynthesis II)	150
3.87	Phenotype 87.	
	POLYAM SYN-PWY (superpathway of polyamine biosynthesis I)	151
3.88	Phenotype 88.	
	POLYISOPREN SYN-PWY (polyisoprenoid biosynthesis (E. coli))	152
3.89	Phenotype 89.	
	PPGPP MET-PWY (ppGpp biosynthesis)	153
3.90	Phenotype 90.	
	PROTocatechuate-ortho-cleavage-PWY (protocatechuate degradation II (ortho-cleavage pathway))	154
3.91	Phenotype 91.	
	PRPP-PWY (superpathway of histidine, purine, and pyrimidine biosynthesis)	155
3.92	Phenotype 92.	
	PWY-1269 (CMP-3-deoxy-D-manno-octulosonate biosynthesis I)	156
3.93	Phenotype 93.	
	PWY-1622 (formaldehyde assimilation I (serine pathway))	157
3.94	Phenotype 94.	
	PWY-181 (photorespiration)	158
3.95	Phenotype 95.	
	PWY-1861 (formaldehyde assimilation II (RuMP Cycle))	159

3.96 Phenotype 96.	
PWY-2941 (L-lysine biosynthesis II)	160
3.97 Phenotype 97.	
PWY-2942 (L-lysine biosynthesis III)	161
3.98 Phenotype 98.	
PWY-3001 (superpathway of L-isoleucine biosynthesis I)	162
3.99 Phenotype 99.	
PWY-3781 (aerobic respiration I (cytochrome c))	163
3.100 Phenotype 100.	
PWY-4984 (urea cycle)	164
3.101 Phenotype 101.	
PWY-5005 (biotin biosynthesis II)	165
3.102 Phenotype 102.	
PWY-5022 (4-aminobutanoate degradation V)	166
3.103 Phenotype 103.	
PWY-5097 (L-lysine biosynthesis VI)	167
3.104 Phenotype 104.	
PWY-5100 (pyruvate fermentation to acetate and lactate II)	168
3.105 Phenotype 105.	
PWY-5101 (L-isoleucine biosynthesis II)	169
3.106 Phenotype 106.	
PWY-5103 (L-isoleucine biosynthesis III)	170
3.107 Phenotype 107.	
PWY-5104 (L-isoleucine biosynthesis IV)	171
3.108 Phenotype 108.	
PWY-5121 (superpathway of geranylgeranyl diphosphate biosynthesis II (via MEP))	172
3.109 Phenotype 109.	
PWY-5154 (L-arginine biosynthesis III (via N-acetyl-L-citrulline))	173
3.110 Phenotype 110.	
PWY-5177 (glutaryl-CoA degradation)	174
3.111 Phenotype 111.	
PWY-5180 (toluene degradation I (aerobic) (via o-cresol))	175
3.112 Phenotype 112.	
PWY-5182 (toluene degradation II (aerobic) (via 4-methylcatechol))	176
3.113 Phenotype 113.	
PWY-5188 (tetrapyrrole biosynthesis I (from glutamate))	177
3.114 Phenotype 114.	
PWY-5189 (tetrapyrrole biosynthesis II (from glycine))	178
3.115 Phenotype 115.	
PWY-5265 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis II (staphylococci))	179
3.116 Phenotype 116.	
PWY-5304 (superpathway of sulfur oxidation (Acidianus ambivalens))	180
3.117 Phenotype 117.	
PWY-5345 (superpathway of L-methionine biosynthesis (by sulfhydrylation))	181

3.118	Phenotype 118.	
	PWY-5347 (superpathway of L-methionine biosynthesis (transsulfuration))	182
3.119	Phenotype 119.	
	PWY-5384 (sucrose degradation IV (sucrose phosphorylase))	183
3.120	Phenotype 120.	
	PWY-5415 (catechol degradation I (meta-cleavage pathway))	184
3.121	Phenotype 121.	
	PWY-5484 (glycolysis II (from fructose 6-phosphate))	185
3.122	Phenotype 122.	
	PWY-5505 (L-glutamate and L-glutamine biosynthesis)	186
3.123	Phenotype 123.	
	PWY-5507 (adenosylcobalamin biosynthesis I (early cobalt insertion))	187
3.124	Phenotype 124.	
	PWY-5509 (adenosylcobalamin biosynthesis from cobyrinate a,c-diamide I)	188
3.125	Phenotype 125.	
	PWY-5659 (GDP-mannose biosynthesis)	189
3.126	Phenotype 126.	
	PWY-5667 (CDP-diacylglycerol biosynthesis I)	190
3.127	Phenotype 127.	
	PWY-5676 (acetyl-CoA fermentation to butanoate II)	191
3.128	Phenotype 128.	
	PWY-5677 (succinate fermentation to butanoate)	192
3.129	Phenotype 129.	
	PWY-5686 (UMP biosynthesis)	193
3.130	Phenotype 130.	
	PWY-5695 (urate biosynthesis/inosine 5'-phosphate degradation)	194
3.131	Phenotype 131.	
	PWY-5705 (allantoin degradation to glyoxylate III)	195
3.132	Phenotype 132.	
	PWY-5741 (ethylmalonyl-CoA pathway)	196
3.133	Phenotype 133.	
	PWY-5747 (2-methylcitrate cycle II)	197
3.134	Phenotype 134.	
	PWY-5837 (1,4-dihydroxy-2-naphthoate biosynthesis I)	198
3.135	Phenotype 135.	
	PWY-5838 (superpathway of menaquinol-8 biosynthesis I)	199
3.136	Phenotype 136.	
	PWY-5840 (superpathway of menaquinol-7 biosynthesis)	200
3.137	Phenotype 137.	
	PWY-5845 (superpathway of menaquinol-9 biosynthesis)	201
3.138	Phenotype 138.	
	PWY-5850 (superpathway of menaquinol-6 biosynthesis I)	202
3.139	Phenotype 139.	
	PWY-5855 (ubiquinol-7 biosynthesis (prokaryotic))	203

3.140	Phenotype 140.	
	PWY-5856 (ubiquinol-9 biosynthesis (prokaryotic))	204
3.141	Phenotype 141.	
	PWY-5857 (ubiquinol-10 biosynthesis (prokaryotic))	205
3.142	Phenotype 142.	
	PWY-5860 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-6 biosynthesis I)	206
3.143	Phenotype 143.	
	PWY-5861 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-8 biosynthesis)	207
3.144	Phenotype 144.	
	PWY-5862 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-9 biosynthesis)	208
3.145	Phenotype 145.	
	PWY-5863 (superpathway of phylloquinol biosynthesis)	209
3.146	Phenotype 146.	
	PWY-5896 (superpathway of menaquinol-10 biosynthesis)	210
3.147	Phenotype 147.	
	PWY-5897 (superpathway of menaquinol-11 biosynthesis)	211
3.148	Phenotype 148.	
	PWY-5898 (superpathway of menaquinol-12 biosynthesis)	212
3.149	Phenotype 149.	
	PWY-5899 (superpathway of menaquinol-13 biosynthesis)	213
3.150	Phenotype 150.	
	PWY-5910 (superpathway of geranylgeranyldiphosphate biosynthesis I (via mevalonate))	214
3.151	Phenotype 151.	
	PWY-5913 (TCA cycle VI (obligate autotrophs))	215
3.152	Phenotype 152.	
	PWY-5918 (superpathway of heme biosynthesis from glutamate)	216
3.153	Phenotype 153.	
	PWY-5920 (superpathway of heme biosynthesis from glycine)	217
3.154	Phenotype 154.	
	PWY-5971 (palmitate biosynthesis II (bacteria and plants))	218
3.155	Phenotype 155.	
	PWY-5973 (cis-vaccenate biosynthesis)	219
3.156	Phenotype 156.	
	PWY-5989 (stearate biosynthesis II (bacteria and plants))	220
3.157	Phenotype 157.	
	PWY-6121 (5-aminoimidazole ribonucleotide biosynthesis I)	221
3.158	Phenotype 158.	
	PWY-6122 (5-aminoimidazole ribonucleotide biosynthesis II)	222
3.159	Phenotype 159.	
	PWY-6123 (inosine-5'-phosphate biosynthesis I)	223
3.160	Phenotype 160.	
	PWY-6125 (superpathway of guanosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)	224
3.161	Phenotype 161.	
	PWY-6126 (superpathway of adenosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)	225

3.162	Phenotype 162.	
	PWY-6147 (6-hydroxymethyl-dihydropterin diphosphate biosynthesis I)	226
3.163	Phenotype 163.	
	PWY-6151 (S-adenosyl-L-methionine cycle I)	227
3.164	Phenotype 164.	
	PWY-6163 (chorismate biosynthesis from 3-dehydroquinate)	228
3.165	Phenotype 165.	
	PWY-621 (sucrose degradation III (sucrose invertase))	229
3.166	Phenotype 166.	
	PWY-6263 (superpathway of menaquinol-8 biosynthesis II)	230
3.167	Phenotype 167.	
	PWY-6269 (adenosylcobalamin salvage from cobinamide II)	231
3.168	Phenotype 168.	
	PWY-6277 (superpathway of 5-aminoimidazole ribonucleotide biosynthesis)	232
3.169	Phenotype 169.	
	PWY-6282 (palmitoleate biosynthesis I (from (5Z)-dodec-5-enoate))	233
3.170	Phenotype 170.	
	PWY-6317 (galactose degradation I (Leloir pathway))	234
3.171	Phenotype 171.	
	PWY-6353 (purine nucleotides degradation II (aerobic))	235
3.172	Phenotype 172.	
	PWY-6383 (mono-trans, poly-cis decaprenyl phosphate biosynthesis)	236
3.173	Phenotype 173.	
	PWY-6385 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis III (mycobacteria))	237
3.174	Phenotype 174.	
	PWY-6386 (UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-pentapeptide biosynthesis II (lysine-containing))	238
3.175	Phenotype 175.	
	PWY-6387 (UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-pentapeptide biosynthesis I (meso-diaminopimelate containing))	239
3.176	Phenotype 176.	
	PWY-6396 (superpathway of 2,3-butanediol biosynthesis)	240
3.177	Phenotype 177.	
	PWY-6397 (mycolyl-arabinogalactan-peptidoglycan complex biosynthesis)	241
3.178	Phenotype 178.	
	PWY-6467 (Kdo transfer to lipid IVA III (Chlamydia))	242
3.179	Phenotype 179.	
	PWY-6470 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis V (β-lactam resistance))	243
3.180	Phenotype 180.	
	PWY-6471 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis IV (Enterococcus faecium))	244
3.181	Phenotype 181.	
	PWY-6478 (GDP-D-glycero-α-D-manno-heptose biosynthesis)	245
3.182	Phenotype 182.	
	PWY-6507 (4-deoxy-L-threo-hex-4-enopyranuronate degradation)	246

3.183	Phenotype 183.	
	PWY-6519 (8-amino-7-oxononanoate biosynthesis I)	247
3.184	Phenotype 184.	
	PWY-6545 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis III)	248
3.185	Phenotype 185.	
	PWY-6562 (norspermidine biosynthesis)	249
3.186	Phenotype 186.	
	PWY-6588 (pyruvate fermentation to acetone)	250
3.187	Phenotype 187.	
	PWY-6590 (superpathway of <i>Clostridium acetobutylicum</i> acidogenic fermentation)	251
3.188	Phenotype 188.	
	PWY-6608 (guanosine nucleotides degradation III)	252
3.189	Phenotype 189.	
	PWY-6609 (adenine and adenosine salvage III)	253
3.190	Phenotype 190.	
	PWY-6612 (superpathway of tetrahydrofolate biosynthesis)	254
3.191	Phenotype 191.	
	PWY-6628 (superpathway of L-phenylalanine biosynthesis)	255
3.192	Phenotype 192.	
	PWY-6630 (superpathway of L-tyrosine biosynthesis)	256
3.193	Phenotype 193.	
	PWY-6700 (queuosine biosynthesis)	257
3.194	Phenotype 194.	
	PWY-6703 (preQ0 biosynthesis)	258
3.195	Phenotype 195.	
	PWY-6708 (ubiquinol-8 biosynthesis (prokaryotic))	259
3.196	Phenotype 196.	
	PWY-6737 (starch degradation V)	260
3.197	Phenotype 197.	
	PWY-6749 (CMP-legionamate biosynthesis I)	261
3.198	Phenotype 198.	
	PWY-6876 (isopropanol biosynthesis)	262
3.199	Phenotype 199.	
	PWY-6891 (thiazole biosynthesis II (<i>Bacillus</i>))	263
3.200	Phenotype 200.	
	PWY-6892 (thiazole biosynthesis I (<i>E. coli</i>))	264
3.201	Phenotype 201.	
	PWY-6895 (superpathway of thiamin diphosphate biosynthesis II)	265
3.202	Phenotype 202.	
	PWY-6897 (thiamin salvage II)	266
3.203	Phenotype 203.	
	PWY-6901 (superpathway of glucose and xylose degradation)	267
3.204	Phenotype 204.	
	PWY-6969 (TCA cycle V (2-oxoglutarate:ferredoxin oxidoreductase))	268

3.205	Phenotype 205.	
	PWY-7003 (glycerol degradation to butanol)	269
3.206	Phenotype 206.	
	PWY-7007 (methyl ketone biosynthesis)	270
3.207	Phenotype 207.	
	PWY-7013 (L-1,2-propanediol degradation)	271
3.208	Phenotype 208.	
	PWY-7094 (fatty acid salvage)	272
3.209	Phenotype 209.	
	PWY-7111 (pyruvate fermentation to isobutanol (engineered))	273
3.210	Phenotype 210.	
	PWY-7159 (chlorophyllide a biosynthesis III (aerobic, light independent))	274
3.211	Phenotype 211.	
	PWY-7184 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis I)	275
3.212	Phenotype 212.	
	PWY-7187 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)	276
3.213	Phenotype 213.	
	PWY-7196 (superpathway of pyrimidine ribonucleosides salvage)	277
3.214	Phenotype 214.	
	PWY-7197 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotide phosphorylation)	278
3.215	Phenotype 215.	
	PWY-7199 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleosides salvage)	279
3.216	Phenotype 216.	
	PWY-7200 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleoside salvage)	280
3.217	Phenotype 217.	
	PWY-7208 (superpathway of pyrimidine nucleobases salvage)	281
3.218	Phenotype 218.	
	PWY-7211 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis)	282
3.219	Phenotype 219.	
	PWY-7219 (adenosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis)	283
3.220	Phenotype 220.	
	PWY-7220 (adenosine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)	284
3.221	Phenotype 221.	
	PWY-7221 (guanosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis)	285
3.222	Phenotype 222.	
	PWY-7222 (guanosine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)	286
3.223	Phenotype 223.	
	PWY-7228 (superpathway of guanosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis I)	287
3.224	Phenotype 224.	
	PWY-7229 (superpathway of adenosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis I)	288
3.225	Phenotype 225.	
	PWY-7234 (inosine-5'-phosphate biosynthesis III)	289
3.226	Phenotype 226.	
	PWY-7237 (myo-, chiro- and scillo-inositol degradation)	290

3.227	Phenotype 227.	
	PWY-7242 (D-fructuronate degradation)	291
3.228	Phenotype 228.	
	PWY-7254 (TCA cycle VII (acetate-producers))	292
3.229	Phenotype 229.	
	PWY-7315 (dTDP-N-acetylthomosamine biosynthesis)	293
3.230	Phenotype 230.	
	PWY-7323 (superpathway of GDP-mannose-derived O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis)	294
3.231	Phenotype 231.	
	PWY-7328 (superpathway of UDP-glucose-derived O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis)	295
3.232	Phenotype 232.	
	PWY-7332 (superpathway of UDP-N-acetylglucosamine-derived O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis)	296
3.233	Phenotype 233.	
	PWY-7371 (1,4-dihydroxy-6-naphthoate biosynthesis II)	297
3.234	Phenotype 234.	
	PWY-7373 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-6 biosynthesis II)	298
3.235	Phenotype 235.	
	PWY-7376 (cob(II)yrinate a,c-diamide biosynthesis II (late cobalt incorporation))	299
3.236	Phenotype 236.	
	PWY-7377 (cob(II)yrinate a,c-diamide biosynthesis I (early cobalt insertion))	300
3.237	Phenotype 237.	
	PWY-7392 (taxadiene biosynthesis (engineered))	301
3.238	Phenotype 238.	
	PWY-7400 (L-arginine biosynthesis IV (archaeobacteria))	302
3.239	Phenotype 239.	
	PWY-7431 (aromatic biogenic amine degradation (bacteria))	303
3.240	Phenotype 240.	
	PWY-7456 (mannan degradation)	304
3.241	Phenotype 241.	
	PWY-7539 (6-hydroxymethyl-dihydropterin diphosphate biosynthesis III (Chlamydia))	305
3.242	Phenotype 242.	
	PWY-7560 (methylerythritol phosphate pathway II)	306
3.243	Phenotype 243.	
	PWY-7663 (gondoate biosynthesis (anaerobic))	307
3.244	Phenotype 244.	
	PWY-7664 (oleate biosynthesis IV (anaerobic))	308
3.245	Phenotype 245.	
	PWY-841 (superpathway of purine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis I)	309
3.246	Phenotype 246.	
	PWY-922 (mevalonate pathway I)	310

3.247	Phenotype 247.	
	PWY0-1061 (superpathway of L-alanine biosynthesis)	311
3.248	Phenotype 248.	
	PWY0-1241 (ADP-L-glycero-β-D-manno-heptose biosynthesis)	312
3.249	Phenotype 249.	
	PWY0-1261 (anhydromuropeptides recycling)	313
3.250	Phenotype 250.	
	PWY0-1296 (purine ribonucleosides degradation)	314
3.251	Phenotype 251.	
	PWY0-1297 (superpathway of purine deoxyribonucleosides degradation)	315
3.252	Phenotype 252.	
	PWY0-1298 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleosides degradation)	316
3.253	Phenotype 253.	
	PWY0-1319 (CDP-diacylglycerol biosynthesis II)	317
3.254	Phenotype 254.	
	PWY0-1415 (superpathway of heme biosynthesis from uroporphyrinogen-III)	318
3.255	Phenotype 255.	
	PWY0-1479 (tRNA processing)	319
3.256	Phenotype 256.	
	PWY0-1533 (methylphosphonate degradation I)	320
3.257	Phenotype 257.	
	PWY0-1586 (peptidoglycan maturation (meso-diaminopimelate containing))	321
3.258	Phenotype 258.	
	PWY0-162 (superpathway of pyrimidine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis)	322
3.259	Phenotype 259.	
	PWY0-166 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis (E. coli))	323
3.260	Phenotype 260.	
	PWY0-321 (phenylacetate degradation I (aerobic))	324
3.261	Phenotype 261.	
	PWY0-42 (2-methylcitrate cycle I)	325
3.262	Phenotype 262.	
	PWY0-781 (aspartate superpathway)	326
3.263	Phenotype 263.	
	PWY0-845 (superpathway of pyridoxal 5'-phosphate biosynthesis and salvage)	327
3.264	Phenotype 264.	
	PWY0-862 ((5Z)-dodec-5-enoate biosynthesis)	328
3.265	Phenotype 265.	
	PWY1G-0 (mycothiol biosynthesis)	329
3.266	Phenotype 266.	
	PWY490-3 (nitrate reduction VI (assimilatory))	330
3.267	Phenotype 267.	
	PWY4FS-7 (phosphatidylglycerol biosynthesis I (plastidic))	331

3.268	Phenotype 268.	
	PWY4FS-8 (phosphatidylglycerol biosynthesis II (non-plastidic))	332
3.269	Phenotype 269.	
	PWYG-321 (mycolate biosynthesis)	333
3.270	Phenotype 270.	
	PYRIDNUCSAL-PWY (NAD salvage pathway I)	334
3.271	Phenotype 271.	
	PYRIDNUCSYN-PWY (NAD biosynthesis I (from aspartate))	335
3.272	Phenotype 272.	
	PYRIDOXSYN-PWY (pyridoxal 5'-phosphate biosynthesis I)	336
3.273	Phenotype 273.	
	REDCITCYC (TCA cycle VIII (helicobacter))	337
3.274	Phenotype 274.	
	RHAMCAT-PWY (L-rhamnose degradation I)	338
3.275	Phenotype 275.	
	RIBOSYN2-PWY (flavin biosynthesis I (bacteria and plants))	339
3.276	Phenotype 276.	
	RUMP-PWY (formaldehyde oxidation I)	340
3.277	Phenotype 277.	
	SALVADEHYPOX-PWY (adenosine nucleotides degradation II)	341
3.278	Phenotype 278.	
	SER-GLYSYN-PWY (superpathway of L-serine and glycine biosynthesis I)	342
3.279	Phenotype 279.	
	SO4ASSIM-PWY (sulfate reduction I (assimilatory))	343
3.280	Phenotype 280.	
	SULFATE-CYS-PWY (superpathway of sulfate assimilation and cysteine biosynthesis)	344
3.281	Phenotype 281.	
	TCA (TCA cycle I (prokaryotic))	345
3.282	Phenotype 282.	
	TCA-GLYOX-BYPASS (superpathway of glyoxylate bypass and TCA)	346
3.283	Phenotype 283.	
	TEICHOICACID-PWY (teichoic acid (poly-glycerol) biosynthesis)	347
3.284	Phenotype 284.	
	THISYN-PWY (superpathway of thiamin diphosphate biosynthesis I)	348
3.285	Phenotype 285.	
	THRESYN-PWY (superpathway of L-threonine biosynthesis)	349
3.286	Phenotype 286.	
	TRNA-CHARGING-PWY (tRNA charging)	350
3.287	Phenotype 287.	
	TRPSYN-PWY (L-tryptophan biosynthesis)	351
3.288	Phenotype 288.	
	TYRFUMCAT-PWY (L-tyrosine degradation I)	352
3.289	Phenotype 289.	
	UBISYN-PWY (superpathway of ubiquinol-8 biosynthesis (prokaryotic))	353

3.290	Phenotype 290.	
	UDPNAGSYN-PWY (UDP-N-acetyl-D-glucosamine biosynthesis I)	354
3.291	Phenotype 291.	
	VALSYN-PWY (L-valine biosynthesis)	355
4	Continuous VBTs (The RAB of bacterial taxa)	355
4.1	Phenotype 1.	
	p_Actinobacteriota (RAB)	356
4.2	Phenotype 2.	
	p_Firmicutes (RAB)	357
4.3	Phenotype 3.	
	p_Proteobacteria (RAB)	358
4.4	Phenotype 4.	
	c_Actinobacteria (RAB)	359
4.5	Phenotype 5.	
	c_Clostridia (RAB)	360
4.6	Phenotype 6.	
	c_Gammaproteobacteria (RAB)	361
4.7	Phenotype 7.	
	o_Bacteroidales (RAB)	362
4.8	Phenotype 8.	
	o_Campylobacterales (RAB)	363
4.9	Phenotype 9.	
	o_Fusobacteriales (RAB)	364
4.10	Phenotype 10.	
	o_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (RAB)	365
4.11	Phenotype 11.	
	f_Aerococcaceae (RAB)	366
4.12	Phenotype 12.	
	f_Bifidobacteriaceae (RAB)	367
4.13	Phenotype 13.	
	f_Lachnospiraceae (RAB)	368
4.14	Phenotype 14.	
	f_Mycoplasmataceae (RAB)	369
4.15	Phenotype 15.	
	f_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (RAB)	370
4.16	Phenotype 16.	
	f_Veillonellaceae (RAB)	371
4.17	Phenotype 17.	
	g_Anaerococcus (RAB)	372
4.18	Phenotype 18.	
	g_Atopobium (RAB)	373
4.19	Phenotype 19.	
	g_Dialister (RAB)	374

4.20	Phenotype 20.	
	g_Lactobacillus (RAB)	375
4.21	Phenotype 21.	
	g_Megasphaera (RAB)	376
4.22	Phenotype 22.	
	g_Peptoniphilus (RAB)	377
4.23	Phenotype 23.	
	g_Prevotella (RAB)	378
4.24	Phenotype 24.	
	g_Streptococcus (RAB)	379
4.25	Phenotype 25.	
	s_Aerococcus christensenii (RAB)	380
4.26	Phenotype 26.	
	s_Atopobium vaginae (RAB)	381
4.27	Phenotype 27.	
	s_Dialister microaerophilus (RAB)	382
4.28	Phenotype 28.	
	s_Dialister propionicifaciens (RAB)	383
4.29	Phenotype 29.	
	s_Finegoldia magna (RAB)	384
4.30	Phenotype 30.	
	s_Gardnerella vaginalis (RAB)	385
4.31	Phenotype 31.	
	s_Lactobacillus crispatus (RAB)	386
4.32	Phenotype 32.	
	s_Lactobacillus iners (RAB)	387
4.33	Phenotype 33.	
	s_Lactobacillus jensenii (RAB)	388
4.34	Phenotype 34.	
	s_Lactobacillus mulieris (RAB)	389
4.35	Phenotype 35.	
	s_Lactobacillus paragasseri/gasseri (RAB)	390
4.36	Phenotype 36.	
	s_Lactobacillus reuteri (RAB)	391
4.37	Phenotype 37.	
	s_Megasphaera genomosp type 1 (RAB)	392
4.38	Phenotype 38.	
	s_Peptoniphilus vaginalis (RAB)	393
4.39	Phenotype 39.	
	s_Prevotella bivia (RAB)	394
4.40	Phenotype 40.	
	s_Prevotella timonensis (RAB)	395

5	Multivariate VBTs (Beta diversity)	395
5.1	Phenotype 1.	
	Bray-curtis Dissimilarity	396
5.2	Phenotype 2.	
	Unweighted Unifrac	397
5.3	Phenotype 3.	
	Weighted Unifrac	398

1 Binary VBTs (The P/A or D/ND of bacterial taxa)

1.1 Phenotype 1. p_Actinobacteriota (P/A)

Figure 1: The association between InDels and p_Actinobacteriota (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.2 Phenotype 2. p_Firmicutes (D/ND)

Figure 2: The association between InDels and p_Firmicutes (D/ND). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.3 Phenotype 3. p_Proteobacteria (P/A)

Figure 3: The association between InDels and p_Proteobacteria (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.4 Phenotype 4. c_Actinobacteria (P/A)

Figure 4: The association between InDels and c_Actinobacteria (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.5 Phenotype 5. c_Clostridia (P/A)

Figure 5: The association between InDels and c_Clostridia (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.6 Phenotype 6. c_Gammaproteobacteria (P/A)

Figure 6: The association between InDels and c_Gammaproteobacteria (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.7 Phenotype 7. o_Bacteroidales (P/A)

Figure 7: The association between InDels and o_Bacteroidales (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.8 Phenotype 8. o_Campylobacteriales (P/A)

Figure 8: The association between InDels and o_Campylobacteriales (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.9 Phenotype 9. o_Fusobacteriales (P/A)

Figure 9: The association between InDels and o_Fusobacteriales (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.10 Phenotype 10. o_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (P/A)

Figure 10: The association between InDels and o_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.11 Phenotype 11. f_Aerococcaceae (P/A)

Figure 11: The association between InDels and f_Aerococcaceae (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.12 Phenotype 12. f_Bifidobacteriaceae (P/A)

Figure 12: The association between InDels and f_Bifidobacteriaceae (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.13 Phenotype 13. f_Lachnospiraceae (P/A)

Figure 13: The association between InDels and f_Lachnospiraceae (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.14 Phenotype 14. f_Mycoplasmataceae (P/A)

Figure 14: The association between InDels and f_Mycoplasmataceae (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.15 Phenotype 15. f_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (P/A)

Figure 15: The association between InDels and f_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.16 Phenotype 16. f_Veillonellaceae (P/A)

Figure 16: The association between InDels and f_Veillonellaceae (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.17 Phenotype 17. g_Anaerococcus (P/A)

Figure 17: The association between InDels and g_Anaerococcus (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.18 Phenotype 18. g_Atopobium (P/A)

Figure 18: The association between InDels and g_Atopobium (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.19 Phenotype 19. g_Dialister (P/A)

Figure 19: The association between InDels and g_Dialister (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.20 Phenotype 20. g_Lactobacillus (D/ND)

Figure 20: The association between InDels and g_Lactobacillus (D/ND). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.21 Phenotype 21. g_Megasphaera (P/A)

Figure 21: The association between InDels and g_Megasphaera (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.22 Phenotype 22. g_Peptoniphilus (P/A)

Figure 22: The association between InDels and g_Peptoniphilus (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.23 Phenotype 23. g_Prevotella (P/A)

Figure 23: The association between InDels and g_Prevotella (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.24 Phenotype 24. g_Streptococcus (P/A)

Figure 24: The association between InDels and g_Streptococcus (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.25 Phenotype 25. s_Aerococcus christensenii (P/A)

Figure 25: The association between InDels and s_Aerococcus christensenii (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.26 Phenotype 26. s_Atopobium vaginae (P/A)

Figure 26: The association between InDels and s_Atopobium vaginae (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.27 Phenotype 27. s_Dialister microaerophilus (P/A)

Figure 27: The association between InDels and s_Dialister microaerophilus (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.28 Phenotype 28. s_Dialister propionicifaciens (P/A)

Figure 28: The association between InDels and s_Dialister propionicifaciens (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.29 Phenotype 29.

s_Finegoldia magna (P/A)

Figure 29: The association between InDels and s_Finegoldia magna (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.30 Phenotype 30. s_Gardnerella vaginalis (P/A)

Figure 30: The association between InDels and s_Gardnerella vaginalis (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.31 Phenotype 31. s_Lactobacillus crispatus (D/ND)

Figure 31: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus crispatus (D/ND). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.32 Phenotype 32. s_Lactobacillus iners (D/ND)

Figure 32: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus iners (D/ND). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.33 Phenotype 33. s_Lactobacillus jensenii (P/A)

Figure 33: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus jensenii (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.34 Phenotype 34. s_Lactobacillus mulieris (P/A)

Figure 34: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus mulieris (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.35 Phenotype 35. s_Lactobacillus paragasseri/gasseri (P/A)

Figure 35: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus paragasseri/gasseri (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.36 Phenotype 36. s_Lactobacillus reuteri (P/A)

Figure 36: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus reuteri (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.37 Phenotype 37. s_Megasphaera genomosp type 1 (P/A)

Figure 37: The association between InDels and s_Megasphaera genomosp type 1 (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.38 Phenotype 38. s_Peptoniphilus vaginalis (P/A)

Figure 38: The association between InDels and s_Peptoniphilus vaginalis (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.39 Phenotype 39. s_Prevotella bivia (P/A)

Figure 39: The association between InDels and s_Prevotella bivia (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

1.40 Phenotype 40. s_Prevotella timonensis (P/A)

Figure 40: The association between InDels and s_Prevotella timonensis (P/A). The upper panel shows the P values returned from logistic regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

2 Continuous VBTs (Alpha diversity)

2.1 Phenotype 1. ASV Richness

Figure 41: The association between InDels and ASV Richness. The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

2.2 Phenotype 2. Shannon Index

Figure 42: The association between InDels and Shannon Index. The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

2.3 Phenotype 3. Faith PD

Figure 43: The association between InDels and Faith PD. The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

2.4 Phenotype 4. Pielou Evenness

Figure 44: The association between InDels and Pielou Evenness. The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3 Continuous VBTs (The extrapolated PICRUSt2 MetaCyc pathways)

3.1 Phenotype 1. 1CMET2-PWY (N10-formyl-tetrahydrofolate biosynthesis)

Figure 45: The association between InDels and 1CMET2-PWY (N10-formyl-tetrahydrofolate biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.2 Phenotype 2.

ALL-CHORISMATE-PWY (superpathway of chorismate metabolism)

Figure 46: The association between InDels and ALL-CHORISMATE-PWY (superpathway of chorismate metabolism). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.3 Phenotype 3. ANAEROFRUCAT-PWY (homolactic fermentation)

Figure 47: The association between InDels and ANAEROFRUCAT-PWY (homolactic fermentation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.4 Phenotype 4.

ANAGLYCOLYSIS-PWY (glycolysis III (from glucose))

Figure 48: The association between InDels and ANAGLYCOLYSIS-PWY (glycolysis III (from glucose)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.5 Phenotype 5.

ARG+POLYAMINE-SYN (superpathway of arginine and polyamine biosynthesis)

Figure 49: The association between InDels and ARG+POLYAMINE-SYN (superpathway of arginine and polyamine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.6 Phenotype 6.

ARGORNPROST-PWY (arginine, ornithine and proline interconversion)

Figure 50: The association between InDels and ARGORNPROST-PWY (arginine, ornithine and proline interconversion). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.7 Phenotype 7.

ARGSYN-PWY (L-arginine biosynthesis I (via L-ornithine))

Figure 51: The association between InDels and ARGSYN-PWY (L-arginine biosynthesis I (via L-ornithine)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.8 Phenotype 8. ARGSYNBSUB-PWY (L-arginine biosynthesis II (acetyl cycle))

Figure 52: The association between InDels and ARGSYNBSUB-PWY (L-arginine biosynthesis II (acetyl cycle)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.9 Phenotype 9. ARO-PWY (chorismate biosynthesis I)

Figure 53: The association between InDels and ARO-PWY (chorismate biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.10 Phenotype 10.

ASPASN-PWY (superpathway of L-aspartate and L-asparagine biosynthesis)

Figure 54: The association between InDels and ASPASN-PWY (superpathway of L-aspartate and L-asparagine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.11 Phenotype 11.

BIOTIN-BIOSYNTHESIS-PWY (biotin biosynthesis I)

Figure 55: The association between InDels and BIOTIN-BIOSYNTHESIS-PWY (biotin biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.12 Phenotype 12.

BRANCHED-CHAIN-AA-SYN-PWY (superpathway of branched amino acid biosynthesis)

Figure 56: The association between InDels and BRANCHED-CHAIN-AA-SYN-PWY (superpathway of branched amino acid biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.13 Phenotype 13. CALVIN-PWY (Calvin-Benson-Bassham cycle)

Figure 57: The association between InDels and CALVIN-PWY (Calvin-Benson-Bassham cycle). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.14 Phenotype 14.

CATECHOL-ORTHO-CLEAVAGE-PWY (catechol degradation to β-ketoacid)

Figure 58: The association between InDels and CATECHOL-ORTHO-CLEAVAGE-PWY (catechol degradation to β-ketoacid). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.15 Phenotype 15. CENTFERM-PWY (pyruvate fermentation to butanoate)

Figure 59: The association between InDels and CENTFERM-PWY (pyruvate fermentation to butanoate). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.16 Phenotype 16. COA-PWY (coenzyme A biosynthesis I)

Figure 60: The association between InDels and COA-PWY (coenzyme A biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.17 Phenotype 17.

COBALSYN-PWY (adenosylcobalamin salvage from cobinamide I)

Figure 61: The association between InDels and COBALSYN-PWY (adenosylcobalamin salvage from cobinamide I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.18 Phenotype 18. CODH-PWY (reductive acetyl coenzyme A pathway)

Figure 62: The association between InDels and CODH-PWY (reductive acetyl coenzyme A pathway). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.19 Phenotype 19. COLANSYN-PWY (colanic acid building blocks biosynthesis)

Figure 63: The association between InDels and COLANSYN-PWY (colanic acid building blocks biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.20 Phenotype 20.

COMPLETE-ARO-PWY (superpathway of aromatic amino acid biosynthesis)

Figure 64: The association between InDels and COMPLETE-ARO-PWY (superpathway of aromatic amino acid biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.21 Phenotype 21. DAPLYSINESYN-PWY (L-lysine biosynthesis I)

Figure 65: The association between InDels and DAPLYSINESYN-PWY (L-lysine biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.22 Phenotype 22.

DENOVOPURINE2-PWY (superpathway of purine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)

Figure 66: The association between InDels and DENOVOPURINE2-PWY (superpathway of purine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.23 Phenotype 23. DTDPRHAMSYN-PWY (dTDP-L-rhamnose biosynthesis I)

Figure 67: The association between InDels and DTDPRHAMSYN-PWY (dTDP-L-rhamnose biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.24 Phenotype 24. ENTBACSYN-PWY (enterobactin biosynthesis)

Figure 68: The association between InDels and ENTBACSYN-PWY (enterobactin biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.25 Phenotype 25. FAO-PWY (fatty acid β-oxidation I)

Figure 69: The association between InDels and FAO-PWY (fatty acid β-oxidation I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.26 Phenotype 26. FASYN-ELONG-PWY (fatty acid elongation – saturated)

Figure 70: The association between InDels and FASYN-ELONG-PWY (fatty acid elongation – saturated). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.27 Phenotype 27.

FASYN-INITIAL-PWY (superpathway of fatty acid biosynthesis initiation (E. coli))

Figure 71: The association between InDels and FASYN-INITIAL-PWY (superpathway of fatty acid biosynthesis initiation (E. coli)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.28 Phenotype 28. FERMENTATION-PWY (mixed acid fermentation)

Figure 72: The association between InDels and FERMENTATION-PWY (mixed acid fermentation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.29 Phenotype 29.

FOLSYN-PWY (superpathway of tetrahydrofolate biosynthesis and salvage)

Figure 73: The association between InDels and FOLSYN-PWY (superpathway of tetrahydrofolate biosynthesis and salvage). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.30 Phenotype 30.

FUC-RHAMCAT-PWY (superpathway of fucose and rhamnose degradation)

Figure 74: The association between InDels and FUC-RHAMCAT-PWY (superpathway of fucose and rhamnose degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.31 Phenotype 31. FUCCAT-PWY (fucose degradation)

Figure 75: The association between InDels and FUCCAT-PWY (fucose degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.32 Phenotype 32.

GALACT-GLUCUROCAT-PWY (superpathway of hexuronide and hexuronate degradation)

Figure 76: The association between InDels and GALACT-GLUCUROCAT-PWY (superpathway of hexuronide and hexuronate degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.33 Phenotype 33. GALACTUROCAT-PWY (D-galacturonate degradation I)

Figure 77: The association between InDels and GALACTUROCAT-PWY (D-galacturonate degradation I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.34 Phenotype 34.

GLCMANNANAUT-PWY (superpathway of N-acetylglucosamine, N-acetylmannosamine and N-acetylneuraminate degradation)

Figure 78: The association between InDels and GLCMANNANAUT-PWY (superpathway of N-acetylglucosamine, N-acetylmannosamine and N-acetylneuraminate degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.35 Phenotype 35. GLUCONEO-PWY (gluconeogenesis I)

Figure 79: The association between InDels and GLUCONEO-PWY (gluconeogenesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.36 Phenotype 36.

GLUCOSE1PMETAB-PWY (glucose and glucose-1-phosphate degradation)

Figure 80: The association between InDels and GLUCOSE1PMETAB-PWY (glucose and glucose-1-phosphate degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.37 Phenotype 37.

GLUCUROCAT-PWY (superpathway of β -D-glucuronide and D-glucuronate degradation)

Figure 81: The association between InDels and GLUCUROCAT-PWY (superpathway of β -D-glucuronide and D-glucuronate degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.38 Phenotype 38. GLUTORN-PWY (L-ornithine biosynthesis)

Figure 82: The association between InDels and GLUTORN-PWY (L-ornithine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.39 Phenotype 39. GLYCOCAT-PWY (glycogen degradation I (bacterial))

Figure 83: The association between InDels and GLYCOCAT-PWY (glycogen degradation I (bacterial)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.40 Phenotype 40.

GLYCOGENSYNTH-PWY (glycogen biosynthesis I (from ADP-D-Glucose))

Figure 84: The association between InDels and GLYCOGENSYNTH-PWY (glycogen biosynthesis I (from ADP-D-Glucose)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.41 Phenotype 41. GLYCOLYSIS (glycolysis I (from glucose 6-phosphate))

Figure 85: The association between InDels and GLYCOLYSIS (glycolysis I (from glucose 6-phosphate)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.42 Phenotype 42.

GLYCOLYSIS-E-D (superpathway of glycolysis and Entner-Doudoroff)

Figure 86: The association between InDels and GLYCOLYSIS-E-D (superpathway of glycolysis and Entner-Doudoroff). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.43 Phenotype 43.

GLYCOLYSIS-TCA-GLYOX-BYPASS (superpathway of glycolysis, pyruvate dehydrogenase, TCA, and glyoxylate bypass)

Figure 87: The association between InDels and GLYCOLYSIS-TCA-GLYOX-BYPASS (superpathway of glycolysis, pyruvate dehydrogenase, TCA, and glyoxylate bypass). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.44 Phenotype 44. GLYOXYLATE-BYPASS (glyoxylate cycle)

Figure 88: The association between InDels and GLYOXYLATE-BYPASS (glyoxylate cycle). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.45 Phenotype 45.

GOLPDLCAT-PWY (superpathway of glycerol degradation to 1,3-propanediol)

Figure 89: The association between InDels and GOLPDLCAT-PWY (superpathway of glycerol degradation to 1,3-propanediol). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.46 Phenotype 46. HEME-BIOSYNTHESIS-II (heme biosynthesis I (aerobic))

Figure 90: The association between InDels and HEME-BIOSYNTHESIS-II (heme biosynthesis I (aerobic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.47 Phenotype 47. HEMESYN2-PWY (heme biosynthesis II (anaerobic))

Figure 91: The association between InDels and HEMESYN2-PWY (heme biosynthesis II (anaerobic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.48 Phenotype 48.

HEXITOLDEGSUPER-PWY (superpathway of hexitol degradation (bacteria))

Figure 92: The association between InDels and HEXITOLDEGSUPER-PWY (superpathway of hexitol degradation (bacteria)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.49 Phenotype 49. HISDEG-PWY (L-histidine degradation I)

Figure 93: The association between InDels and HISDEG-PWY (L-histidine degradation I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.50 Phenotype 50. HISTSYN-PWY (L-histidine biosynthesis)

Figure 94: The association between InDels and HISTSYN-PWY (L-histidine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.51 Phenotype 51. HOMOSER-METSYN-PWY (L-methionine biosynthesis I)

Figure 95: The association between InDels and HOMOSER-METSYN-PWY (L-methionine biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.52 Phenotype 52. HSERMETANA-PWY (L-methionine biosynthesis III)

Figure 96: The association between InDels and HSERMETANA-PWY (L-methionine biosynthesis III). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.53 Phenotype 53.

ILEUSYN-PWY (L-isoleucine biosynthesis I (from threonine))

Figure 97: The association between InDels and ILEUSYN-PWY (L-isoleucine biosynthesis I (from threonine)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.54 Phenotype 54.

KDO-NAGLIPASYN-PWY (superpathway of (Kdo)2-lipid A biosynthesis)

Figure 98: The association between InDels and KDO-NAGLIPASYN-PWY (superpathway of (Kdo)2-lipid A biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.55 Phenotype 55. LACTOSECAT-PWY (lactose and galactose degradation I)

Figure 99: The association between InDels and LACTOSECAT-PWY (lactose and galactose degradation I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.56 Phenotype 56. LEU-DEG2-PWY (L-leucine degradation I)

Figure 100: The association between InDels and LEU-DEG2-PWY (L-leucine degradation I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.57 Phenotype 57.

MET-SAM-PWY (superpathway of S-adenosyl-L-methionine biosynthesis)

Figure 101: The association between InDels and MET-SAM-PWY (superpathway of S-adenosyl-L-methionine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.58 Phenotype 58. METH-ACETATE-PWY (methanogenesis from acetate)

Figure 102: The association between InDels and METH-ACETATE-PWY (methanogenesis from acetate). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.59 Phenotype 59. NAD-BIOSYNTHESIS-II (NAD salvage pathway II)

Figure 103: The association between InDels and NAD-BIOSYNTHESIS-II (NAD salvage pathway II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.60 Phenotype 60. NAGLIPASYN-PWY (lipid IVA biosynthesis)

Figure 104: The association between InDels and NAGLIPASYN-PWY (lipid IVA biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.61 Phenotype 61.

NONMEVIPP-PWY (methylethritol phosphate pathway I)

Figure 105: The association between InDels and NONMEVIPP-PWY (methylethritol phosphate pathway I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.62 Phenotype 62.

NONOXIPENT-PWY (pentose phosphate pathway (non-oxidative branch))

Figure 106: The association between InDels and NONOXIPENT-PWY (pentose phosphate pathway (non-oxidative branch)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.63 Phenotype 63.

OANTIGEN-PWY (O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis (E. coli))

Figure 107: The association between InDels and OANTIGEN-PWY (O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis (E. coli)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.64 Phenotype 64. P105-PWY (TCA cycle IV (2-oxoglutarate decarboxylase))

Figure 108: The association between InDels and P105-PWY (TCA cycle IV (2-oxoglutarate decarboxylase)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.65 Phenotype 65. P108-PWY (pyruvate fermentation to propanoate I)

Figure 109: The association between InDels and P108-PWY (pyruvate fermentation to propanoate I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.66 Phenotype 66. P122-PWY (heterolactic fermentation)

Figure 110: The association between InDels and P122-PWY (heterolactic fermentation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.67 Phenotype 67. P124-PWY (Bifidobacterium shunt)

Figure 111: The association between InDels and P124-PWY (Bifidobacterium shunt). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.68 Phenotype 68. P125-PWY (superpathway of (R,R)-butanediol biosynthesis)

Figure 112: The association between InDels and P125-PWY (superpathway of (R,R)-butanediol biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.69 Phenotype 69. P161-PWY (acetylene degradation)

Figure 113: The association between InDels and P161-PWY (acetylene degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.70 Phenotype 70.

P162-PWY (L-glutamate degradation V (via hydroxyglutarate))

Figure 114: The association between InDels and P162-PWY (L-glutamate degradation V (via hydroxyglutarate)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.71 Phenotype 71. P163-PWY (L-lysine fermentation to acetate and butanoate)

Figure 115: The association between InDels and P163-PWY (L-lysine fermentation to acetate and butanoate). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.72 Phenotype 72.

P164-PWY (purine nucleobases degradation I (anaerobic))

Figure 116: The association between InDels and P164-PWY (purine nucleobases degradation I (anaerobic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.73 Phenotype 73. P221-PWY (octane oxidation)

Figure 117: The association between InDels and P221-PWY (octane oxidation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.74 Phenotype 74. P23-PWY (reductive TCA cycle I)

Figure 118: The association between InDels and P23-PWY (reductive TCA cycle I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.75 Phenotype 75.

P381-PWY (adenosylcobalamin biosynthesis II (late cobalt incorporation))

Figure 119: The association between InDels and P381-PWY (adenosylcobalamin biosynthesis II (late cobalt incorporation)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.76 Phenotype 76.

P4-PWY (superpathway of L-lysine, L-threonine and L-methionine biosynthesis I)

Figure 120: The association between InDels and P4-PWY (superpathway of L-lysine, L-threonine and L-methionine biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.77 Phenotype 77. P42-PWY (incomplete reductive TCA cycle)

Figure 121: The association between InDels and P42-PWY (incomplete reductive TCA cycle). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.78 Phenotype 78.

P441-PWY (superpathway of N-acetylneuraminate degradation)

Figure 122: The association between InDels and P441-PWY (superpathway of N-acetylneuraminate degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.79 Phenotype 79.

P461-PWY (hexitol fermentation to lactate, formate, ethanol and acetate)

Figure 123: The association between InDels and P461-PWY (hexitol fermentation to lactate, formate, ethanol and acetate). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.80 Phenotype 80. P562-PWY (myo-inositol degradation I)

Figure 124: The association between InDels and P562-PWY (myo-inositol degradation I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.81 Phenotype 81. PANTO-PWY (phosphopantothenate biosynthesis I)

Figure 125: The association between InDels and PANTO-PWY (phosphopantothenate biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.82 Phenotype 82.

PANTOSYN-PWY (pantothenate and coenzyme A biosynthesis I)

Figure 126: The association between InDels and PANTOSYN-PWY (pantothenate and coenzyme A biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.83 Phenotype 83. PENTOSE-P-PWY (pentose phosphate pathway)

Figure 127: The association between InDels and PENTOSE-P-PWY (pentose phosphate pathway). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.84 Phenotype 84.

PEPTIDOGLYCANSYN-PWY (peptidoglycan biosynthesis I (meso-diaminopimelate containing))

Figure 128: The association between InDels and PEPTIDOGLYCANSYN-PWY (peptidoglycan biosynthesis I (meso-diaminopimelate containing)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.85 Phenotype 85.

PHOSLIPSYN-PWY (superpathway of phospholipid biosynthesis I (bacteria))

Figure 129: The association between InDels and PHOSLIPSYN-PWY (superpathway of phospholipid biosynthesis I (bacteria)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.86 Phenotype 86. POLYAMINSYN3-PWY (superpathway of polyamine biosynthesis II)

Figure 130: The association between InDels and POLYAMINSYN3-PWY (superpathway of polyamine biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.87 Phenotype 87.

POLYAMSYN-PWY (superpathway of polyamine biosynthesis I)

Figure 131: The association between InDels and POLYAMSYN-PWY (superpathway of polyamine biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.88 Phenotype 88. POLYISOPRENSYN-PWY (polyisoprenoid biosynthesis (E. coli))

Figure 132: The association between InDels and POLYISOPRENSYN-PWY (polyisoprenoid biosynthesis (E. coli)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.89 Phenotype 89. PPGPPMET-PWY (ppGpp biosynthesis)

Figure 133: The association between InDels and PPGPPMET-PWY (ppGpp biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.90 Phenotype 90.

PROTocatechuate-ortho-cleavage-PWY (protocatechuate degradation II (ortho-cleavage pathway))

Figure 134: The association between InDels and PROTocatechuate-ortho-cleavage-PWY (protocatechuate degradation II (ortho-cleavage pathway)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.91 Phenotype 91.

PRPP-PWY (superpathway of histidine, purine, and pyrimidine biosynthesis)

Figure 135: The association between InDels and PRPP-PWY (superpathway of histidine, purine, and pyrimidine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.92 Phenotype 92.

PWY-1269 (CMP-3-deoxy-D-manno-octulosonate biosynthesis I)

Figure 136: The association between InDels and PWY-1269 (CMP-3-deoxy-D-manno-octulosonate biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.93 Phenotype 93. PWY-1622 (formaldehyde assimilation I (serine pathway))

Figure 137: The association between InDels and PWY-1622 (formaldehyde assimilation I (serine pathway)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.94 Phenotype 94. PWY-181 (photorespiration)

Figure 138: The association between InDels and PWY-181 (photorespiration). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.95 Phenotype 95. PWY-1861 (formaldehyde assimilation II (RuMP Cycle))

Figure 139: The association between InDels and PWY-1861 (formaldehyde assimilation II (RuMP Cycle)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.96 Phenotype 96. PWY-2941 (L-lysine biosynthesis II)

Figure 140: The association between InDels and PWY-2941 (L-lysine biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.97 Phenotype 97. PWY-2942 (L-lysine biosynthesis III)

Figure 141: The association between InDels and PWY-2942 (L-lysine biosynthesis III). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.98 Phenotype 98. PWY-3001 (superpathway of L-isoleucine biosynthesis I)

Figure 142: The association between InDels and PWY-3001 (superpathway of L-isoleucine biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.99 Phenotype 99. PWY-3781 (aerobic respiration I (cytochrome c))

Figure 143: The association between InDels and PWY-3781 (aerobic respiration I (cytochrome c)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.100 Phenotype 100. PWY-4984 (urea cycle)

Figure 144: The association between InDels and PWY-4984 (urea cycle). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.101 Phenotype 101. PWY-5005 (biotin biosynthesis II)

Figure 145: The association between InDels and PWY-5005 (biotin biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.102 Phenotype 102. PWY-5022 (4-aminobutanoate degradation V)

Figure 146: The association between InDels and PWY-5022 (4-aminobutanoate degradation V). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.103 Phenotype 103. PWY-5097 (L-lysine biosynthesis VI)

Figure 147: The association between InDels and PWY-5097 (L-lysine biosynthesis VI). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.104 Phenotype 104.

PWY-5100 (pyruvate fermentation to acetate and lactate II)

Figure 148: The association between InDels and PWY-5100 (pyruvate fermentation to acetate and lactate II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.105 Phenotype 105. PWY-5101 (L-isoleucine biosynthesis II)

Figure 149: The association between InDels and PWY-5101 (L-isoleucine biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.106 Phenotype 106. PWY-5103 (L-isoleucine biosynthesis III)

Figure 150: The association between InDels and PWY-5103 (L-isoleucine biosynthesis III). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.107 Phenotype 107. PWY-5104 (L-isoleucine biosynthesis IV)

Figure 151: The association between InDels and PWY-5104 (L-isoleucine biosynthesis IV). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.108 Phenotype 108.

PWY-5121 (superpathway of geranylgeranyl diphosphate biosynthesis II (via MEP))

Figure 152: The association between InDels and PWY-5121 (superpathway of geranylgeranyl diphosphate biosynthesis II (via MEP)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.109 Phenotype 109.

PWY-5154 (L-arginine biosynthesis III (via N-acetyl-L-citrulline))

Figure 153: The association between InDels and PWY-5154 (L-arginine biosynthesis III (via N-acetyl-L-citrulline)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.110 Phenotype 110. PWY-5177 (glutaryl-CoA degradation)

Figure 154: The association between InDels and PWY-5177 (glutaryl-CoA degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.111 Phenotype 111.

PWY-5180 (toluene degradation I (aerobic) (via o-cresol))

Figure 155: The association between InDels and PWY-5180 (toluene degradation I (aerobic) (via o-cresol)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.112 Phenotype 112.

PWY-5182 (toluene degradation II (aerobic) (via 4-methylcatechol))

Figure 156: The association between InDels and PWY-5182 (toluene degradation II (aerobic) (via 4-methylcatechol)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.113 Phenotype 113.

PWY-5188 (tetrapyrrole biosynthesis I (from glutamate))

Figure 157: The association between InDels and PWY-5188 (tetrapyrrole biosynthesis I (from glutamate)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.114 Phenotype 114.

PWY-5189 (tetrapyrrole biosynthesis II (from glycine))

Figure 158: The association between InDels and PWY-5189 (tetrapyrrole biosynthesis II (from glycine)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.115 Phenotype 115. PWY-5265 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis II (staphylococci))

Figure 159: The association between InDels and PWY-5265 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis II (staphylococci)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.116 Phenotype 116.

PWY-5304 (superpathway of sulfur oxidation (*Acidianus ambivalens*))

Figure 160: The association between InDels and PWY-5304 (superpathway of sulfur oxidation (*Acidianus ambivalens*)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.117 Phenotype 117.

PWY-5345 (superpathway of L-methionine biosynthesis (by sulfhydrylation))

Figure 161: The association between InDels and PWY-5345 (superpathway of L-methionine biosynthesis (by sulfhydrylation)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.118 Phenotype 118.

PWY-5347 (superpathway of L-methionine biosynthesis (transsulfuration))

Figure 162: The association between InDels and PWY-5347 (superpathway of L-methionine biosynthesis (transsulfuration)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.119 Phenotype 119.

PWY-5384 (sucrose degradation IV (sucrose phosphorylase))

Figure 163: The association between InDels and PWY-5384 (sucrose degradation IV (sucrose phosphorylase)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.120 Phenotype 120.

PWY-5415 (catechol degradation I (meta-cleavage pathway))

Figure 164: The association between InDels and PWY-5415 (catechol degradation I (meta-cleavage pathway)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.121 Phenotype 121. PWY-5484 (glycolysis II (from fructose 6-phosphate))

Figure 165: The association between InDels and PWY-5484 (glycolysis II (from fructose 6-phosphate)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.122 Phenotype 122. PWY-5505 (L-glutamate and L-glutamine biosynthesis)

Figure 166: The association between InDels and PWY-5505 (L-glutamate and L-glutamine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.123 Phenotype 123.

PWY-5507 (adenosylcobalamin biosynthesis I (early cobalt insertion))

Figure 167: The association between InDels and PWY-5507 (adenosylcobalamin biosynthesis I (early cobalt insertion)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.124 Phenotype 124.

PWY-5509 (adenosylcobalamin biosynthesis from cobyrinate a,c-diamide I)

Figure 168: The association between InDels and PWY-5509 (adenosylcobalamin biosynthesis from cobyrinate a,c-diamide I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.125 Phenotype 125. PWY-5659 (GDP-mannose biosynthesis)

Figure 169: The association between InDels and PWY-5659 (GDP-mannose biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.126 Phenotype 126. PWY-5667 (CDP-diacylglycerol biosynthesis I)

Figure 170: The association between InDels and PWY-5667 (CDP-diacylglycerol biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.127 Phenotype 127. PWY-5676 (acetyl-CoA fermentation to butanoate II)

Figure 171: The association between InDels and PWY-5676 (acetyl-CoA fermentation to butanoate II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.128 Phenotype 128. PWY-5677 (succinate fermentation to butanoate)

Figure 172: The association between InDels and PWY-5677 (succinate fermentation to butanoate). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.129 Phenotype 129. PWY-5686 (UMP biosynthesis)

Figure 173: The association between InDels and PWY-5686 (UMP biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.130 Phenotype 130.

PWY-5695 (urate biosynthesis/inosine 5'-phosphate degradation)

Figure 174: The association between InDels and PWY-5695 (urate biosynthesis/inosine 5'-phosphate degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.131 Phenotype 131. PWY-5705 (allantoin degradation to glyoxylate III)

Figure 175: The association between InDels and PWY-5705 (allantoin degradation to glyoxylate III). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.132 Phenotype 132. PWY-5741 (ethylmalonyl-CoA pathway)

Figure 176: The association between InDels and PWY-5741 (ethylmalonyl-CoA pathway). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.133 Phenotype 133. PWY-5747 (2-methylcitrate cycle II)

Figure 177: The association between InDels and PWY-5747 (2-methylcitrate cycle II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.134 Phenotype 134.

PWY-5837 (1,4-dihydroxy-2-naphthoate biosynthesis I)

Figure 178: The association between InDels and PWY-5837 (1,4-dihydroxy-2-naphthoate biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.135 Phenotype 135. PWY-5838 (superpathway of menaquinol-8 biosynthesis I)

Figure 179: The association between InDels and PWY-5838 (superpathway of menaquinol-8 biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.136 Phenotype 136. PWY-5840 (superpathway of menaquinol-7 biosynthesis)

Figure 180: The association between InDels and PWY-5840 (superpathway of menaquinol-7 biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.137 Phenotype 137. PWY-5845 (superpathway of menaquinol-9 biosynthesis)

Figure 181: The association between InDels and PWY-5845 (superpathway of menaquinol-9 biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.138 Phenotype 138. PWY-5850 (superpathway of menaquinol-6 biosynthesis I)

Figure 182: The association between InDels and PWY-5850 (superpathway of menaquinol-6 biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.139 Phenotype 139. PWY-5855 (ubiquinol-7 biosynthesis (prokaryotic))

Figure 183: The association between InDels and PWY-5855 (ubiquinol-7 biosynthesis (prokaryotic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.140 Phenotype 140. PWY-5856 (ubiquinol-9 biosynthesis (prokaryotic))

Figure 184: The association between InDels and PWY-5856 (ubiquinol-9 biosynthesis (prokaryotic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.141 Phenotype 141.

PWY-5857 (ubiquinol-10 biosynthesis (prokaryotic))

Figure 185: The association between InDels and PWY-5857 (ubiquinol-10 biosynthesis (prokaryotic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.142 Phenotype 142.

PWY-5860 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-6 biosynthesis I)

Figure 186: The association between InDels and PWY-5860 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-6 biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.143 Phenotype 143.

PWY-5861 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-8 biosynthesis)

Figure 187: The association between InDels and PWY-5861 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-8 biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.144 Phenotype 144.

PWY-5862 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-9 biosynthesis)

Figure 188: The association between InDels and PWY-5862 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-9 biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.145 Phenotype 145. PWY-5863 (superpathway of phylloquinol biosynthesis)

Figure 189: The association between InDels and PWY-5863 (superpathway of phylloquinol biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.146 Phenotype 146. PWY-5896 (superpathway of menaquinol-10 biosynthesis)

Figure 190: The association between InDels and PWY-5896 (superpathway of menaquinol-10 biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.147 Phenotype 147. PWY-5897 (superpathway of menaquinol-11 biosynthesis)

Figure 191: The association between InDels and PWY-5897 (superpathway of menaquinol-11 biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.148 Phenotype 148. PWY-5898 (superpathway of menaquinol-12 biosynthesis)

Figure 192: The association between InDels and PWY-5898 (superpathway of menaquinol-12 biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.149 Phenotype 149. PWY-5899 (superpathway of menaquinol-13 biosynthesis)

Figure 193: The association between InDels and PWY-5899 (superpathway of menaquinol-13 biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.150 Phenotype 150.

PWY-5910 (superpathway of geranylgeranyldiphosphate biosynthesis I (via mevalonate))

Figure 194: The association between InDels and PWY-5910 (superpathway of geranylgeranyldiphosphate biosynthesis I (via mevalonate)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.151 Phenotype 151. PWY-5913 (TCA cycle VI (obligate autotrophs))

Figure 195: The association between InDels and PWY-5913 (TCA cycle VI (obligate autotrophs)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.152 Phenotype 152.

PWY-5918 (superpathway of heme biosynthesis from glutamate)

Figure 196: The association between InDels and PWY-5918 (superpathway of heme biosynthesis from glutamate). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.153 Phenotype 153.

PWY-5920 (superpathway of heme biosynthesis from glycine)

Figure 197: The association between InDels and PWY-5920 (superpathway of heme biosynthesis from glycine). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.154 Phenotype 154.

PWY-5971 (palmitate biosynthesis II (bacteria and plants))

Figure 198: The association between InDels and PWY-5971 (palmitate biosynthesis II (bacteria and plants)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.155 Phenotype 155. PWY-5973 (cis-vaccenate biosynthesis)

Figure 199: The association between InDels and PWY-5973 (cis-vaccenate biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.156 Phenotype 156.

PWY-5989 (stearate biosynthesis II (bacteria and plants))

Figure 200: The association between InDels and PWY-5989 (stearate biosynthesis II (bacteria and plants)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.157 Phenotype 157.

PWY-6121 (5-aminoimidazole ribonucleotide biosynthesis I)

Figure 201: The association between InDels and PWY-6121 (5-aminoimidazole ribonucleotide biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.158 Phenotype 158. PWY-6122 (5-aminoimidazole ribonucleotide biosynthesis II)

Figure 202: The association between InDels and PWY-6122 (5-aminoimidazole ribonucleotide biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.159 Phenotype 159. PWY-6123 (inosine-5'-phosphate biosynthesis I)

Figure 203: The association between InDels and PWY-6123 (inosine-5'-phosphate biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.160 Phenotype 160.

PWY-6125 (superpathway of guanosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)

Figure 204: The association between InDels and PWY-6125 (superpathway of guanosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.161 Phenotype 161.

PWY-6126 (superpathway of adenosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)

Figure 205: The association between InDels and PWY-6126 (superpathway of adenosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.162 Phenotype 162.

PWY-6147 (6-hydroxymethyl-dihydropterin diphosphate biosynthesis I)

Figure 206: The association between InDels and PWY-6147 (6-hydroxymethyl-dihydropterin diphosphate biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.163 Phenotype 163. PWY-6151 (S-adenosyl-L-methionine cycle I)

Figure 207: The association between InDels and PWY-6151 (S-adenosyl-L-methionine cycle I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.164 Phenotype 164. PWY-6163 (chorismate biosynthesis from 3-dehydroquinate)

Figure 208: The association between InDels and PWY-6163 (chorismate biosynthesis from 3-dehydroquinate). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.165 Phenotype 165.

PWY-621 (sucrose degradation III (sucrose invertase))

Figure 209: The association between InDels and PWY-621 (sucrose degradation III (sucrose invertase)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.166 Phenotype 166. PWY-6263 (superpathway of menaquinol-8 biosynthesis II)

Figure 210: The association between InDels and PWY-6263 (superpathway of menaquinol-8 biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.167 Phenotype 167.

PWY-6269 (adenosylcobalamin salvage from cobinamide II)

Figure 211: The association between InDels and PWY-6269 (adenosylcobalamin salvage from cobinamide II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.168 Phenotype 168.

PWY-6277 (superpathway of 5-aminoimidazole ribonucleotide biosynthesis)

Figure 212: The association between InDels and PWY-6277 (superpathway of 5-aminoimidazole ribonucleotide biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.169 Phenotype 169.

PWY-6282 (palmitoleate biosynthesis I (from (5Z)-dodec-5-enoate))

Figure 213: The association between InDels and PWY-6282 (palmitoleate biosynthesis I (from (5Z)-dodec-5-enoate)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.170 Phenotype 170.

PWY-6317 (galactose degradation I (Leloir pathway))

Figure 214: The association between InDels and PWY-6317 (galactose degradation I (Leloir pathway)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.171 Phenotype 171. PWY-6353 (purine nucleotides degradation II (aerobic))

Figure 215: The association between InDels and PWY-6353 (purine nucleotides degradation II (aerobic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.172 Phenotype 172.

PWY-6383 (mono-trans, poly-cis decaprenyl phosphate biosynthesis)

Figure 216: The association between InDels and PWY-6383 (mono-trans, poly-cis decaprenyl phosphate biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.173 Phenotype 173.

PWY-6385 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis III (mycobacteria))

Figure 217: The association between InDels and PWY-6385 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis III (mycobacteria)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.174 Phenotype 174.

PWY-6386 (UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-pentapeptide biosynthesis II (lysine-containing))

Figure 218: The association between InDels and PWY-6386 (UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-pentapeptide biosynthesis II (lysine-containing)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.175 Phenotype 175.

PWY-6387 (UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-pentapeptide biosynthesis I (meso-diaminopimelate containing))

Figure 219: The association between InDels and PWY-6387 (UDP-N-acetylmuramoyl-pentapeptide biosynthesis I (meso-diaminopimelate containing)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.176 Phenotype 176. PWY-6396 (superpathway of 2,3-butanediol biosynthesis)

Figure 220: The association between InDels and PWY-6396 (superpathway of 2,3-butanediol biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.177 Phenotype 177.

PWY-6397 (mycolyl-arabinogalactan-peptidoglycan complex biosynthesis)

Figure 221: The association between InDels and PWY-6397 (mycolyl-arabinogalactan-peptidoglycan complex biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.178 Phenotype 178. PWY-6467 (Kdo transfer to lipid IVA III (Chlamydia))

Figure 222: The association between InDels and PWY-6467 (Kdo transfer to lipid IVA III (Chlamydia)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.179 Phenotype 179.

PWY-6470 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis V (β-lactam resistance))

Figure 223: The association between InDels and PWY-6470 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis V (β-lactam resistance)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.180 Phenotype 180.

PWY-6471 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis IV (*Enterococcus faecium*))

Figure 224: The association between InDels and PWY-6471 (peptidoglycan biosynthesis IV (*Enterococcus faecium*)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.181 Phenotype 181.

PWY-6478 (GDP-D-glycero-α-D-manno-heptose biosynthesis)

Figure 225: The association between InDels and PWY-6478 (GDP-D-glycero-α-D-manno-heptose biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.182 Phenotype 182. PWY-6507 (4-deoxy-L-threo-hex-4-enopyranuronate degradation)

Figure 226: The association between InDels and PWY-6507 (4-deoxy-L-threo-hex-4-enopyranuronate degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.183 Phenotype 183. PWY-6519 (8-amino-7-oxononanoate biosynthesis I)

Figure 227: The association between InDels and PWY-6519 (8-amino-7-oxononanoate biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.184 Phenotype 184.

PWY-6545 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis III)

Figure 228: The association between InDels and PWY-6545 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis III). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.185 Phenotype 185. PWY-6562 (norspermidine biosynthesis)

Figure 229: The association between InDels and PWY-6562 (norspermidine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.186 Phenotype 186. PWY-6588 (pyruvate fermentation to acetone)

Figure 230: The association between InDels and PWY-6588 (pyruvate fermentation to acetone). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.187 Phenotype 187.

PWY-6590 (superpathway of *Clostridium acetobutylicum* acidogenic fermentation)

Figure 231: The association between InDels and PWY-6590 (superpathway of *Clostridium acetobutylicum* acidogenic fermentation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.188 Phenotype 188. PWY-6608 (guanosine nucleotides degradation III)

Figure 232: The association between InDels and PWY-6608 (guanosine nucleotides degradation III). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.189 Phenotype 189. PWY-6609 (adenine and adenosine salvage III)

Figure 233: The association between InDels and PWY-6609 (adenine and adenosine salvage III). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.190 Phenotype 190. PWY-6612 (superpathway of tetrahydrofolate biosynthesis)

Figure 234: The association between InDels and PWY-6612 (superpathway of tetrahydrofolate biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.191 Phenotype 191. PWY-6628 (superpathway of L-phenylalanine biosynthesis)

Figure 235: The association between InDels and PWY-6628 (superpathway of L-phenylalanine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.192 Phenotype 192. PWY-6630 (superpathway of L-tyrosine biosynthesis)

Figure 236: The association between InDels and PWY-6630 (superpathway of L-tyrosine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.193 Phenotype 193. PWY-6700 (queuosine biosynthesis)

Figure 237: The association between InDels and PWY-6700 (queuosine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.194 Phenotype 194. PWY-6703 (preQ0 biosynthesis)

Figure 238: The association between InDels and PWY-6703 (preQ0 biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.195 Phenotype 195. PWY-6708 (ubiquinol-8 biosynthesis (prokaryotic))

Figure 239: The association between InDels and PWY-6708 (ubiquinol-8 biosynthesis (prokaryotic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.196 Phenotype 196. PWY-6737 (starch degradation V)

Figure 240: The association between InDels and PWY-6737 (starch degradation V). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.197 Phenotype 197. PWY-6749 (CMP-legionamate biosynthesis I)

Figure 241: The association between InDels and PWY-6749 (CMP-legionamate biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.198 Phenotype 198. PWY-6876 (isopropanol biosynthesis)

Figure 242: The association between InDels and PWY-6876 (isopropanol biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.199 Phenotype 199. PWY-6891 (thiazole biosynthesis II (Bacillus))

Figure 243: The association between InDels and PWY-6891 (thiazole biosynthesis II (Bacillus)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.200 Phenotype 200. PWY-6892 (thiazole biosynthesis I (E. coli))

Figure 244: The association between InDels and PWY-6892 (thiazole biosynthesis I (E. coli)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.201 Phenotype 201. PWY-6895 (superpathway of thiamin diphosphate biosynthesis II)

Figure 245: The association between InDels and PWY-6895 (superpathway of thiamin diphosphate biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.202 Phenotype 202. PWY-6897 (thiamin salvage II)

Figure 246: The association between InDels and PWY-6897 (thiamin salvage II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.203 Phenotype 203. PWY-6901 (superpathway of glucose and xylose degradation)

Figure 247: The association between InDels and PWY-6901 (superpathway of glucose and xylose degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.204 Phenotype 204.

PWY-6969 (TCA cycle V (2-oxoglutarate:ferredoxin oxidoreductase))

Figure 248: The association between InDels and PWY-6969 (TCA cycle V (2-oxoglutarate:ferredoxin oxidoreductase)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.205 Phenotype 205. PWY-7003 (glycerol degradation to butanol)

Figure 249: The association between InDels and PWY-7003 (glycerol degradation to butanol). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.206 Phenotype 206. PWY-7007 (methyl ketone biosynthesis)

Figure 250: The association between InDels and PWY-7007 (methyl ketone biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.207 Phenotype 207. PWY-7013 (L-1,2-propanediol degradation)

Figure 251: The association between InDels and PWY-7013 (L-1,2-propanediol degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.208 Phenotype 208. PWY-7094 (fatty acid salvage)

Figure 252: The association between InDels and PWY-7094 (fatty acid salvage). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.209 Phenotype 209.

PWY-7111 (pyruvate fermentation to isobutanol (engineered))

Figure 253: The association between InDels and PWY-7111 (pyruvate fermentation to isobutanol (engineered)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.210 Phenotype 210.

PWY-7159 (chlorophyllide a biosynthesis III (aerobic, light independent))

Figure 254: The association between InDels and PWY-7159 (chlorophyllide a biosynthesis III (aerobic, light independent)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.211 Phenotype 211.

PWY-7184 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis I)

Figure 255: The association between InDels and PWY-7184 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.212 Phenotype 212.

PWY-7187 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)

Figure 256: The association between InDels and PWY-7187 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.213 Phenotype 213.

PWY-7196 (superpathway of pyrimidine ribonucleosides salvage)

Figure 257: The association between InDels and PWY-7196 (superpathway of pyrimidine ribonucleosides salvage). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.214 Phenotype 214.

PWY-7197 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotide phosphorylation)

Figure 258: The association between InDels and PWY-7197 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotide phosphorylation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.215 Phenotype 215.

PWY-7199 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleosides salvage)

Figure 259: The association between InDels and PWY-7199 (pyrimidine deoxyribonucleosides salvage). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.216 Phenotype 216.

PWY-7200 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleoside salvage)

Figure 260: The association between InDels and PWY-7200 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleoside salvage). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.217 Phenotype 217.

PWY-7208 (superpathway of pyrimidine nucleobases salvage)

Figure 261: The association between InDels and PWY-7208 (superpathway of pyrimidine nucleobases salvage). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.218 Phenotype 218.

PWY-7211 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis)

Figure 262: The association between InDels and PWY-7211 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.219 Phenotype 219.

PWY-7219 (adenosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis)

Figure 263: The association between InDels and PWY-7219 (adenosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.220 Phenotype 220. PWY-7220 (adenosine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)

Figure 264: The association between InDels and PWY-7220 (adenosine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.221 Phenotype 221.

PWY-7221 (guanosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis)

Figure 265: The association between InDels and PWY-7221 (guanosine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.222 Phenotype 222. PWY-7222 (guanosine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis II)

Figure 266: The association between InDels and PWY-7222 (guanosine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.223 Phenotype 223.

PWY-7228 (superpathway of guanosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis I)

Figure 267: The association between InDels and PWY-7228 (superpathway of guanosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.224 Phenotype 224.

PWY-7229 (superpathway of adenosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis I)

Figure 268: The association between InDels and PWY-7229 (superpathway of adenosine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.225 Phenotype 225. PWY-7234 (inosine-5'-phosphate biosynthesis III)

Figure 269: The association between InDels and PWY-7234 (inosine-5'-phosphate biosynthesis III). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.226 Phenotype 226. PWY-7237 (myo-, chiro- and scillo-inositol degradation)

Figure 270: The association between InDels and PWY-7237 (myo-, chiro- and scillo-inositol degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.227 Phenotype 227. PWY-7242 (D-fructuronate degradation)

Figure 271: The association between InDels and PWY-7242 (D-fructuronate degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.228 Phenotype 228. PWY-7254 (TCA cycle VII (acetate-producers))

Figure 272: The association between InDels and PWY-7254 (TCA cycle VII (acetate-producers)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.229 Phenotype 229. PWY-7315 (dTDP-N-acetylthomosamine biosynthesis)

Figure 273: The association between InDels and PWY-7315 (dTDP-N-acetylthomosamine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.230 Phenotype 230.

PWY-7323 (superpathway of GDP-mannose-derived O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis)

Figure 274: The association between InDels and PWY-7323 (superpathway of GDP-mannose-derived O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.231 Phenotype 231.

PWY-7328 (superpathway of UDP-glucose-derived O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis)

Figure 275: The association between InDels and PWY-7328 (superpathway of UDP-glucose-derived O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.232 Phenotype 232.

PWY-7332 (superpathway of UDP-N-acetylglucosamine-derived O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis)

Figure 276: The association between InDels and PWY-7332 (superpathway of UDP-N-acetylglucosamine-derived O-antigen building blocks biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.233 Phenotype 233. PWY-7371 (1,4-dihydroxy-6-naphthoate biosynthesis II)

Figure 277: The association between InDels and PWY-7371 (1,4-dihydroxy-6-naphthoate biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.234 Phenotype 234.

PWY-7373 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-6 biosynthesis II)

Figure 278: The association between InDels and PWY-7373 (superpathway of demethylmenaquinol-6 biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.235 Phenotype 235.

PWY-7376 (cob(II)yrinate a,c-diamide biosynthesis II (late cobalt incorporation))

Figure 279: The association between InDels and PWY-7376 (cob(II)yrinate a,c-diamide biosynthesis II (late cobalt incorporation)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.236 Phenotype 236.

PWY-7377 (cob(II)yrrinate a,c-diamide biosynthesis I (early cobalt insertion))

Figure 280: The association between InDels and PWY-7377 (cob(II)yrrinate a,c-diamide biosynthesis I (early cobalt insertion)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.237 Phenotype 237. PWY-7392 (taxadiene biosynthesis (engineered))

Figure 281: The association between InDels and PWY-7392 (taxadiene biosynthesis (engineered)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.238 Phenotype 238. PWY-7400 (L-arginine biosynthesis IV (archaeobacteria))

Figure 282: The association between InDels and PWY-7400 (L-arginine biosynthesis IV (archaeobacteria)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.239 Phenotype 239. PWY-7431 (aromatic biogenic amine degradation (bacteria))

Figure 283: The association between InDels and PWY-7431 (aromatic biogenic amine degradation (bacteria)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.240 Phenotype 240. PWY-7456 (mannan degradation)

Figure 284: The association between InDels and PWY-7456 (mannan degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.241 Phenotype 241.

PWY-7539 (6-hydroxymethyl-dihydropterin diphosphate biosynthesis III (Chlamydia))

Figure 285: The association between InDels and PWY-7539 (6-hydroxymethyl-dihydropterin diphosphate biosynthesis III (Chlamydia)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.242 Phenotype 242. PWY-7560 (methylerythritol phosphate pathway II)

Figure 286: The association between InDels and PWY-7560 (methylerythritol phosphate pathway II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.243 Phenotype 243. PWY-7663 (gondoate biosynthesis (anaerobic))

Figure 287: The association between InDels and PWY-7663 (gondoate biosynthesis (anaerobic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.244 Phenotype 244. PWY-7664 (oleate biosynthesis IV (anaerobic))

Figure 288: The association between InDels and PWY-7664 (oleate biosynthesis IV (anaerobic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.245 Phenotype 245.

PWY-841 (superpathway of purine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis I)

Figure 289: The association between InDels and PWY-841 (superpathway of purine nucleotides de novo biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.246 Phenotype 246. PWY-922 (mevalonate pathway I)

Figure 290: The association between InDels and PWY-922 (mevalonate pathway I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.247 Phenotype 247. PWY0-1061 (superpathway of L-alanine biosynthesis)

Figure 291: The association between InDels and PWY0-1061 (superpathway of L-alanine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.248 Phenotype 248.

PWY0-1241 (ADP-L-glycero-β-D-manno-heptose biosynthesis)

Figure 292: The association between InDels and PWY0-1241 (ADP-L-glycero-β-D-manno-heptose biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.249 Phenotype 249. PWY0-1261 (anhydromuropeptides recycling)

Figure 293: The association between InDels and PWY0-1261 (anhydromuropeptides recycling). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.250 Phenotype 250. PWY0-1296 (purine ribonucleosides degradation)

Figure 294: The association between InDels and PWY0-1296 (purine ribonucleosides degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.251 Phenotype 251.

PWY0-1297 (superpathway of purine deoxyribonucleosides degradation)

Figure 295: The association between InDels and PWY0-1297 (superpathway of purine deoxyribonucleosides degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.252 Phenotype 252.

PWY0-1298 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleosides degradation)

Figure 296: The association between InDels and PWY0-1298 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleosides degradation). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.253 Phenotype 253. PWY0-1319 (CDP-diacylglycerol biosynthesis II)

Figure 297: The association between InDels and PWY0-1319 (CDP-diacylglycerol biosynthesis II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.254 Phenotype 254.

PWY0-1415 (superpathway of heme biosynthesis from uroporphyrinogen-III)

Figure 298: The association between InDels and PWY0-1415 (superpathway of heme biosynthesis from uroporphyrinogen-III). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.255 Phenotype 255. PWY0-1479 (tRNA processing)

Figure 299: The association between InDels and PWY0-1479 (tRNA processing). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.256 Phenotype 256. PWY0-1533 (methylphosphonate degradation I)

Figure 300: The association between InDels and PWY0-1533 (methylphosphonate degradation I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.257 Phenotype 257.

PWY0-1586 (peptidoglycan maturation (meso-diaminopimelate containing))

Figure 301: The association between InDels and PWY0-1586 (peptidoglycan maturation (meso-diaminopimelate containing)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.258 Phenotype 258.

PWY0-162 (superpathway of pyrimidine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis)

Figure 302: The association between InDels and PWY0-162 (superpathway of pyrimidine ribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.259 Phenotype 259.

PWY0-166 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis (E. coli))

Figure 303: The association between InDels and PWY0-166 (superpathway of pyrimidine deoxyribonucleotides de novo biosynthesis (E. coli)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.260 Phenotype 260. PWY0-321 (phenylacetate degradation I (aerobic))

Figure 304: The association between InDels and PWY0-321 (phenylacetate degradation I (aerobic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.261 Phenotype 261. PWY0-42 (2-methylcitrate cycle I)

Figure 305: The association between InDels and PWY0-42 (2-methylcitrate cycle I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.262 Phenotype 262. PWY0-781 (aspartate superpathway)

Figure 306: The association between InDels and PWY0-781 (aspartate superpathway). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.263 Phenotype 263.

PWY0-845 (superpathway of pyridoxal 5'-phosphate biosynthesis and salvage)

Figure 307: The association between InDels and PWY0-845 (superpathway of pyridoxal 5'-phosphate biosynthesis and salvage). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.264 Phenotype 264. PWY0-862 ((5Z)-dodec-5-enoate biosynthesis)

Figure 308: The association between InDels and PWY0-862 ((5Z)-dodec-5-enoate biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.265 Phenotype 265. PWY1G-0 (mycothiol biosynthesis)

Figure 309: The association between InDels and PWY1G-0 (mycothiol biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.266 Phenotype 266. PWY490-3 (nitrate reduction VI (assimilatory))

Figure 310: The association between InDels and PWY490-3 (nitrate reduction VI (assimilatory)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.267 Phenotype 267.

PWY4FS-7 (phosphatidylglycerol biosynthesis I (plastidic))

Figure 311: The association between InDels and PWY4FS-7 (phosphatidylglycerol biosynthesis I (plastidic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.268 Phenotype 268. PWY4FS-8 (phosphatidylglycerol biosynthesis II (non-plastidic))

Figure 312: The association between InDels and PWY4FS-8 (phosphatidylglycerol biosynthesis II (non-plastidic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.269 Phenotype 269. PWYG-321 (mycolate biosynthesis)

Figure 313: The association between InDels and PWYG-321 (mycolate biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.270 Phenotype 270. PYRIDNUCSAL-PWY (NAD salvage pathway I)

Figure 314: The association between InDels and PYRIDNUCSAL-PWY (NAD salvage pathway I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.271 Phenotype 271.

PYRIDNUCSYN-PWY (NAD biosynthesis I (from aspartate))

Figure 315: The association between InDels and PYRIDNUCSYN-PWY (NAD biosynthesis I (from aspartate)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.272 Phenotype 272.

PYRIDOXSYN-PWY (pyridoxal 5'-phosphate biosynthesis I)

Figure 316: The association between InDels and PYRIDOXSYN-PWY (pyridoxal 5'-phosphate biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.273 Phenotype 273. REDCITCYC (TCA cycle VIII (helicobacter))

Figure 317: The association between InDels and REDCITCYC (TCA cycle VIII (helicobacter)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.274 Phenotype 274. RHAMCAT-PWY (L-rhamnose degradation I)

Figure 318: The association between InDels and RHAMCAT-PWY (L-rhamnose degradation I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.275 Phenotype 275. RIBOSYN2-PWY (flavin biosynthesis I (bacteria and plants))

Figure 319: The association between InDels and RIBOSYN2-PWY (flavin biosynthesis I (bacteria and plants)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.276 Phenotype 276. RUMP-PWY (formaldehyde oxidation I)

Figure 320: The association between InDels and RUMP-PWY (formaldehyde oxidation I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.277 Phenotype 277.

SALVADEHYPOX-PWY (adenosine nucleotides degradation II)

Figure 321: The association between InDels and SALVADEHYPOX-PWY (adenosine nucleotides degradation II). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.278 Phenotype 278.

SER-GLYSYN-PWY (superpathway of L-serine and glycine biosynthesis I)

Figure 322: The association between InDels and SER-GLYSYN-PWY (superpathway of L-serine and glycine biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.279 Phenotype 279. SO4ASSIM-PWY (sulfate reduction I (assimilatory))

Figure 323: The association between InDels and SO4ASSIM-PWY (sulfate reduction I (assimilatory)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.280 Phenotype 280.

SULFATE-CYS-PWY (superpathway of sulfate assimilation and cysteine biosynthesis)

Figure 324: The association between InDels and SULFATE-CYS-PWY (superpathway of sulfate assimilation and cysteine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.281 Phenotype 281. TCA (TCA cycle I (prokaryotic))

Figure 325: The association between InDels and TCA (TCA cycle I (prokaryotic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.282 Phenotype 282.

TCA-GLYOX-BYPASS (superpathway of glyoxylate bypass and TCA)

Figure 326: The association between InDels and TCA-GLYOX-BYPASS (superpathway of glyoxylate bypass and TCA). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.283 Phenotype 283.

TEICHOICACID-PWY (teichoic acid (poly-glycerol) biosynthesis)

Figure 327: The association between InDels and TEICHOICACID-PWY (teichoic acid (poly-glycerol) biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.284 Phenotype 284.

THISYN-PWY (superpathway of thiamin diphosphate biosynthesis I)

Figure 328: The association between InDels and THISYN-PWY (superpathway of thiamin diphosphate biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.285 Phenotype 285.

THRESYN-PWY (superpathway of L-threonine biosynthesis)

Figure 329: The association between InDels and THRESYN-PWY (superpathway of L-threonine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.286 Phenotype 286. TRNA-CHARGING-PWY (tRNA charging)

Figure 330: The association between InDels and TRNA-CHARGING-PWY (tRNA charging). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.287 Phenotype 287. TRPSYN-PWY (L-tryptophan biosynthesis)

Figure 331: The association between InDels and TRPSYN-PWY (L-tryptophan biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.288 Phenotype 288. TYRFUMCAT-PWY (L-tyrosine degradation I)

Figure 332: The association between InDels and TYRFUMCAT-PWY (L-tyrosine degradation I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.289 Phenotype 289.

UBISYN-PWY (superpathway of ubiquinol-8 biosynthesis (prokaryotic))

Figure 333: The association between InDels and UBISYN-PWY (superpathway of ubiquinol-8 biosynthesis (prokaryotic)). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.290 Phenotype 290. UDPNAGSYN-PWY (UDP-N-acetyl-D-glucosamine biosynthesis I)

Figure 334: The association between InDels and UDPNAGSYN-PWY (UDP-N-acetyl-D-glucosamine biosynthesis I). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

3.291 Phenotype 291. VALSYN-PWY (L-valine biosynthesis)

Figure 335: The association between InDels and VALSYN-PWY (L-valine biosynthesis). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4 Continuous VBTs (The RAB of bacterial taxa)

4.1 Phenotype 1. p_Actinobacteriota (RAB)

Figure 336: The association between InDels and p_Actinobacteriota (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.2 Phenotype 2. p_Firmicutes (RAB)

Figure 337: The association between InDels and p_Firmicutes (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.3 Phenotype 3. p_Proteobacteria (RAB)

Figure 338: The association between InDels and p_Proteobacteria (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.4 Phenotype 4. c_Actinobacteria (RAB)

Figure 339: The association between InDels and c_Actinobacteria (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.5 Phenotype 5. c_Clostridia (RAB)

Figure 340: The association between InDels and c_Clostridia (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.6 Phenotype 6. c_Gammaproteobacteria (RAB)

Figure 341: The association between InDels and c_Gammaproteobacteria (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.7 Phenotype 7. o_Bacteroidales (RAB)

Figure 342: The association between InDels and o_Bacteroidales (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.8 Phenotype 8. o_Campylobacteriales (RAB)

Figure 343: The association between InDels and o_Campylobacteriales (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.9 Phenotype 9. o_Fusobacteriales (RAB)

Figure 344: The association between InDels and o_Fusobacteriales (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.10 Phenotype 10.

o_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (RAB)

Figure 345: The association between InDels and o_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.11 Phenotype 11. f_Aerococcaceae (RAB)

Figure 346: The association between InDels and f_Aerococcaceae (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.12 Phenotype 12. f_Bifidobacteriaceae (RAB)

Figure 347: The association between InDels and f_Bifidobacteriaceae (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.13 Phenotype 13. f_Lachnospiraceae (RAB)

Figure 348: The association between InDels and f_Lachnospiraceae (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.14 Phenotype 14. f_Mycoplasmataceae (RAB)

Figure 349: The association between InDels and f_Mycoplasmataceae (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.15 Phenotype 15. f_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (RAB)

Figure 350: The association between InDels and f_Peptostreptococcales-Tissierellales (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.16 Phenotype 16. f_Veillonellaceae (RAB)

Figure 351: The association between InDels and f_Veillonellaceae (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.17 Phenotype 17. g_Anaerococcus (RAB)

Figure 352: The association between InDels and g_Anaerococcus (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.18 Phenotype 18. g_Atopobium (RAB)

Figure 353: The association between InDels and g_Atopobium (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.19 Phenotype 19. g_Dialister (RAB)

Figure 354: The association between InDels and g_Dialister (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.20 Phenotype 20. g_Lactobacillus (RAB)

Figure 355: The association between InDels and g_Lactobacillus (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.21 Phenotype 21. g_Megasphaera (RAB)

Figure 356: The association between InDels and g_Megasphaera (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.22 Phenotype 22. g_Peptoniphilus (RAB)

Figure 357: The association between InDels and g_Peptoniphilus (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.23 Phenotype 23. g_Prevotella (RAB)

Figure 358: The association between InDels and g_Prevotella (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.24 Phenotype 24. g_Streptococcus (RAB)

Figure 359: The association between InDels and g_Streptococcus (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.25 Phenotype 25. s_Aerococcus christensenii (RAB)

Figure 360: The association between InDels and s_Aerococcus christensenii (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.26 Phenotype 26. s_Atopobium vaginae (RAB)

Figure 361: The association between InDels and s_Atopobium vaginae (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.27 Phenotype 27. s_Dialister micraerophilus (RAB)

Figure 362: The association between InDels and s_Dialister micraerophilus (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.28 Phenotype 28. s_Dialister propionificiens (RAB)

Figure 363: The association between InDels and s_Dialister propionificiens (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.29 Phenotype 29. s_Finegoldia magna (RAB)

Figure 364: The association between InDels and s_Finegoldia magna (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.30 Phenotype 30. s_Gardnerella vaginalis (RAB)

Figure 365: The association between InDels and s_Gardnerella vaginalis (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.31 Phenotype 31. s_Lactobacillus crispatus (RAB)

Figure 366: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus crispatus (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.32 Phenotype 32. s_Lactobacillus iners (RAB)

Figure 367: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus iners (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.33 Phenotype 33. s_Lactobacillus jensenii (RAB)

Figure 368: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus jensenii (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.34 Phenotype 34. s_Lactobacillus mulieris (RAB)

Figure 369: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus mulieris (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.35 Phenotype 35. s_Lactobacillus paragasseri/gasseri (RAB)

Figure 370: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus paragasseri/gasseri (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.36 Phenotype 36. s_Lactobacillus reuteri (RAB)

Figure 371: The association between InDels and s_Lactobacillus reuteri (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.37 Phenotype 37. s_Megasphaera genomosp type 1 (RAB)

Figure 372: The association between InDels and s_Megasphaera genomosp type 1 (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.38 Phenotype 38. s_Peptoniphilus vaginalis (RAB)

Figure 373: The association between InDels and s_Peptoniphilus vaginalis (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.39 Phenotype 39. s_Prevotella bivia (RAB)

Figure 374: The association between InDels and s_Prevotella bivia (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

4.40 Phenotype 40. s_Prevotella timonensis (RAB)

Figure 375: The association between InDels and s_Prevotella timonensis (RAB). The upper panel shows the P values returned from linear regression model, while the lower panel shows the corresponding effects.

5 Multivariate VBTs (Beta diversity)

5.1 Phenotype 1. Bray-curtis Dissimilarity

Figure 376: The association between InDels and Bray-curtis Dissimilarity. The upper panel shows the P values returned from MANOVA, while the lower panel shows the Pillai's trace.

5.2 Phenotype 2. Unweighted Unifrac

Figure 377: The association between InDels and Unweighted Unifrac. The upper panel shows the P values returned from MANOVA, while the lower panel shows the Pillai's trace.

5.3 Phenotype 3. Weighted Unifrac

Figure 378: The association between InDels and Weighted Unifrac. The upper panel shows the P values returned from MANOVA, while the lower panel shows the Pillai's trace.